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ABSTRACT:

The Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project accelerates digital transformation in humanities and cultural heritage by establishing a collaborative cluster of the Italian nodes of European research infrastructures. Funded by the EU and Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), it aims at promoting open science through CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT. By offering accessible, FAIR-aligned digital resources, H2IOSC supports innovative research and collaboration across sectors, positioning itself as a national model for open, interoperable digital ecosystems. This interim report, "Workflow to Ensure Interoperability for Language Resources and Tools" (D4.8), outlines the methodologies, workflows, and tools that support resource interoperability within CLARIN. The report introduces a framework that includes metadata standards, such as the Component Metadata Infrastructure (CMDI) and the CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR), which ensure consistency and usability of language resources across CLARIN repositories. It also highlights essential tools like the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), Federated Content Search (FCS), and Language Resource Switchboard (LRS), which enhance resource discovery and access across disciplines.

A great effort has been spent towards the development of an ontology, thought of as an expansion of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) and SSHOCro ontology, to model relationships among language resources, tools, and concepts, thereby advancing semantic interoperability. Case studies, including the ParlaMint project, illustrate how standardized metadata and harmonized frameworks enable cross-linguistic, comparative research. By detailing workflows and best practices for metadata creation, management, and discovery, this report establishes a roadmap for integrating diverse language resources and tools into a cohesive, interoperable ecosystem within H2IOSC broader domain.

This document demonstrates H2IOSC's dedication to advancing open science in the humanities and cultural heritage fields, aligning with the European Open Science Cloud's (EOSC) goals for collaborative, data-driven research. The project sets a new benchmark for interoperability and open access in research infrastructures, fostering an inclusive, interdisciplinary approach to data sharing and usage.

Executive Summary

The "Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud" (H2IOSC) project, funded by the European Union's NextGenerationEU and Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), aims to drive digital transformation in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. H2IOSC connects Italian nodes from four key European research infrastructures (CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RHS.it, and OPERAS-IT) to establish a collaborative, interoperable digital ecosystem. This initiative supports open science by providing accessible, FAIR-aligned (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) resources, fostering innovative research and cross-sector collaboration.

This interim report, "Workflow to Ensure Interoperability for Language Resources and Tools" (D4.8), is a deliverable produced within Work Package 4. It outlines a comprehensive framework to achieve interoperability across H2IOSC's ecosystem by describing the working principles of CLARIN Semantic Framework. The report emphasizes the role of metadata standards, including the Component Metadata Infrastructure (CMDI) and the CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR), which ensure consistency and usability of language resources. These frameworks are complemented by advanced tools such as the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), Federated Content Search (FCS), and Language Resource Switchboard (LRS), which facilitate resource discovery, access, and use across disciplines.

A core advancement highlighted in the report is the development of an ontology to model relationships among language resources, tools, and scholarly concepts, taking CLARIN Semantic Framework as the core environmental foundation. This ontology, inspired by and extension of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) and the SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro), advances semantic interoperability, enabling standardized data alignment across multiple domains. This semantic framework underpins multilingual and multidisciplinary research, making it easier for scholars to conduct cross-linguistic, comparative analyses.

The report also details practical workflows for metadata creation, management, and harvesting, essential for ensuring the integration of diverse resources into CLARIN unified infrastructure. Through protocols like OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting), metadata is harmonized and made accessible, enhancing the discoverability of resources. Case studies, including the ParlaMint project, demonstrate the real-world application of these interoperability frameworks, showing how standardized metadata and harmonized ontologies enable collaborative research on European parliamentary proceedings.

CLARIN's efforts align with the objectives of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), advancing a shared vision of collaborative, data-driven research. By setting new standards for interoperability, metadata management, and semantic alignment, CLARIN, under the scope of H2IOSC project, establishes a national and European benchmark for open science in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. This document serves as both a roadmap and a testament to H2IOSC's commitment to fostering inclusive, interdisciplinary research and innovation, ensuring the long-term sustainability of digital resources and tools.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

SSH	Social Science and Humanities
H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
RI	Research Infrastructure
CLARIN-IT	Nodo italiano di CLARIN - Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH-IT	Nodo italiano dell'infrastruttura di ricerca europea DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)
E-RIHS	Nodo italiano dell'infrastruttura di ricerca europea E-RIHS sull'Heritage Science
OPERAS	Nodo italiano dell'infrastruttura europea OPERAS - Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ERA	European Research Area

1. Introduction

This deliverable, titled “Workflow to Ensure Interoperability for Language Resources and Tools” (D4.8), is an interim report for Work Package 4 of the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project. H2IOSC is a flagship initiative funded by the European Union’s NextGenerationEU program and Italy’s National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), designed to facilitate the digital transformation of the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. By establishing a collaborative network that connects Italian nodes of key European research infrastructures— CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT— H2IOSC seeks to promote the principles of open science and ensure the seamless interoperability of digital resources across different platforms, thus fostering enhanced research collaboration.

This report focuses on the critical issue of interoperability, which is fundamental to enabling effective collaboration, data sharing, and resource integration across multiple research disciplines and technological frameworks. The primary aim of this deliverable is to outline a comprehensive workflow for ensuring that language resources and tools within the CLARIN ecosystem are interoperable within the broader H2IOSC ecosystem. Interoperability is essential not only for facilitating data sharing across borders and disciplines but also for aligning with the European Open Science Cloud’s (EOSC) vision, which promotes the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles. By adhering to these principles, H2IOSC aims to empower data-driven, interdisciplinary research, providing high-quality, accessible digital resources that can be used across various technical and organizational platforms.

The document begins with an in-depth look at the CLARIN infrastructure, detailing how it supports access to language data and facilitates scholarly collaboration within the humanities and social sciences. CLARIN's federated network of language resource repositories, service centres, and knowledge hubs provides robust access to multilingual data, offering Single Sign-On (SSO) capabilities and integrating essential tools such as the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO). Through VLO, researchers gain access to advanced metadata frameworks, search, and discovery features that enable the retrieval and use of language resources from across Europe and beyond. This infrastructure is also designed to support multidisciplinary research agendas by offering harmonized access to language data, making it a valuable asset for European research initiatives.

In addition to its focus on language resources, CLARIN plays a pivotal role in the broader H2IOSC project by contributing to the development of a Common Semantic Framework that will guide the interoperability of diverse digital resources across the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. The CLARIN Semantic Framework, with its emphasis on language resources and tools, serves as a foundational component of this larger vision. It ensures that language data and associated tools are integrated into a unified ecosystem that supports semantic interoperability, making language resources both accessible and usable within a wide range of research contexts. As H2IOSC progresses, this framework will expand to encompass other areas of cultural heritage and humanities research, providing a common structure for representing and linking diverse datasets and research tools. By formalizing this Common

Semantic Framework, H2IOSC will facilitate a more interconnected and cohesive digital environment for researchers across disciplines.

Building on this foundational understanding, the report delves into the specific tools and methodologies employed by CLARIN to enhance resource discovery and ensure effective usage. A central focus is on interoperability standards such as the Component Metadata Infrastructure (CMDI) and the CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR). The CMDI framework provides a flexible and standardized approach to metadata, ensuring that metadata across different repositories is consistent and can be used across disciplines. CMDI enables the use of shared metadata profiles that align with domain-specific standards, while the CCR serves as the semantic layer that ensures the standardized use of metadata, enhancing both machine and human interpretability. These frameworks work together to create an integrated environment where language resources and tools can be easily accessed and used.

In addition to metadata standards and frameworks, the report outlines practical workflows for the creation and curation of metadata. It discusses how standards such as the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) streamline the processes of metadata creation, harvesting, and discovery. The report also presents tools like the Federated Content Search (FCS) and the Language Resource Switchboard (LRS), which enable users to access distributed language resources within the CLARIN network without needing to know the specific location of the data. These tools significantly enhance the ease of access to diverse resources, making it easier for researchers to engage with multilingual data and collaborate across disciplines.

The report further includes case studies that demonstrate successful implementations of interoperability within the H2IOSC framework. One notable example is the ParlaMint project, which harmonized European parliamentary data into a unified corpus. This case study highlights how consistent metadata standards and encoding frameworks can facilitate comparative research and cross-border collaborations, providing a tangible example of how interoperability can lead to significant advancements in research. These case studies serve as concrete evidence of CLARIN's commitment to ensuring that diverse language resources are integrated into a cohesive, interoperable ecosystem.

One of the core advancements presented in this report is the development of an ontology designed to model the relationships among language resources, tools, and scholarly concepts, with the CLARIN Semantic Framework serving as its foundational environment. Building on and extending established models such as the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) and the SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro), this ontology enhances semantic interoperability, enabling standardized data alignment across multiple domains. By providing a robust semantic framework, the ontology supports multilingual and multidisciplinary research, facilitating cross-linguistic and comparative analyses while fostering deeper integration and collaboration across diverse research fields. This work also paves the way for the development of a H2IOSC Reference Ontology (H2IOSCro), an expanded framework that represents a key outcome of WP4's efforts. H2IOSCro will further

enhance H2IOSC's ability to represent, share, and analyse resources in a unified, interoperable environment, driving innovation and cohesion within the ecosystem.

In conclusion, this deliverable reinforces H2IOSC's dedication to advancing interoperability as a crucial enabler of open science, particularly within the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. By detailing the workflows, tools, and metadata infrastructures that support effective data interoperability, this report serves as a roadmap for integrating language resources into a unified, accessible, and collaborative digital environment. This approach aligns with the long-term vision of the European Open Science Cloud and positions H2IOSC as a national model for open science practices. By establishing standardized workflows, robust metadata frameworks, and an ontology-driven approach to resource integration, H2IOSC sets a new benchmark for resource sharing, accessibility, and interdisciplinary collaboration in the digital humanities and cultural heritage fields. Furthermore, by linking the CLARIN Semantic Framework to the broader H2IOSC Common Semantic Framework, this report lays the groundwork for creating a unified and extensible digital infrastructure that will foster seamless integration and innovation across multiple disciplines in the years to come.

2. CLARIN domain and focus

CLARIN, the Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure, is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) dedicated to providing easy and sustainable access to digital language resources and tools for scholars, researchers, students, and citizen-scientists in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). By fostering a networked federation of language data repositories, service centres, and centres of expertise, CLARIN enables seamless access to a vast array of language data and services across Europe and beyond.

This section explores the multifaceted offerings of CLARIN, highlighting its commitment to open science and adherence to FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). We delve into the types of language resources available—ranging from corpora and lexicons to advanced language processing tools—and discuss how CLARIN's central services like the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), Federated Content Search (FCS), and Language Resource Switchboard (LRS) enhance discoverability and usability of these resources. Then, we take a look at CLARIN Resource Families, that give an overview description of language resources and tools that are used in CLARIN domain.

By integrating resources and tools through a unified infrastructure, CLARIN not only preserves essential language data but also promotes collaboration and innovation within the SSH disciplines. The initiative aligns with broader European efforts such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the SSH Open Marketplace, positioning itself as a cornerstone in advancing multilingual research and supporting emerging research agendas in language and communication.

2.1 CLARIN value proposition

CLARIN is a networked federation of language data repositories, service centres, and centres of expertise, dedicated to providing easy, long-term access to digital language resources and tools for scholars, researchers, students, and citizen-scientists, especially in the Social Sciences and Humanities. Through single sign-on (SSO) access, CLARIN supports cutting-edge, data-driven research across disciplines by offering sustainable and interoperable technology services for deploying, connecting, and analysing language data, and is committed to contributing to a multilingual European Research Area. With a mission to build and maintain infrastructure for sharing and sustaining language data and tools, CLARIN envisions seamless access to language resources from across Europe and beyond, fostering research in the SSH field. By promoting reuse and repurposing of language data, CLARIN opens new research avenues that address language's role as a cultural and scientific medium, an identity marker, and a tool for cognition and expression.

As an open science advocate, CLARIN aligns with FAIR data principles, aiming to interconnect researchers across national and disciplinary borders by providing unified access to data and services. The infrastructure's distributed model includes centres across Europe, such as universities, research institutions, libraries, and archives, which collaborate to ensure that data collections and tools are interoperable and can be combined to achieve research goals at varying levels of complexity. CLARIN's commitment to interoperability and

support for multidisciplinary collaboration aligns it with initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the SSH Open Marketplace.

Founded in 2012 as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), CLARIN was selected by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) for the European Research Infrastructures Roadmap, achieving ESFRI Landmark status in 2016. Through collaborations with stakeholders from academia, research archives, and the data industry, CLARIN continues to advance its role in supporting emerging SSH research agendas and innovation in data and tool interaction.

CLARIN is open to anyone interested in working with language resources, providing access to a wide array of repositories where resources can be stored, accessed, and shared. These resources fall into three main categories: data, services, and tools, and include datasets that cover various aspects like language, modality, and time span. CLARIN also offers researcher-focused gateway applications, such as a search engine for language resources and applications for discovering, exploring, annotating, analysing, or combining language data. Users can access protected data and services by logging in with their institutional credentials (federated identity) in the form of a single sign-on (SSO) access; CLARIN is continuously working to expand the list of participating identity federations in order to offer its services to a growing broader public.

2.2 Language Resources

The term "Language Resources" traditionally refers to large collections of language data and descriptions in machine-readable format, which are essential for building, enhancing, or evaluating natural language, speech, or multimodal algorithms and systems. Common examples include written, spoken, or multimodal corpora, lexicons, grammars, terminologies, multimodal resources, ontologies, and translation memories. The term also encompasses basic software tools used for acquisition, preparation, annotation, collection, management, and utilisation of these resources. The creation and use of language resources span several related but somewhat separate disciplines, such as natural language processing, information retrieval, machine translation, speech technology, and multimodality.

CLARIN supports this broader definition, acknowledging the necessity to expand the term in light of recent advances in science, methodology, technology, and social and organisational aspects across fields involved in content processing, access, understanding, and creation, as well as in Human-Machine, Human-Human, and Machine-Machine communication. These advances draw from diverse foundational disciplines, including linguistics, cognitive science, artificial intelligence, and robotics.

2.3 CLARIN 4 points of access: technologies and services

CLARIN ERIC, with a vast network of over 70 data centres, is designed to provide seamless access to language resources for researchers, offering tools and repositories across Europe and beyond. This access is possible thanks to CLARIN's central services, which streamline language resources discovery and use. Through its portal, researchers can explore resources

without needing prior knowledge of specific data locations. The Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) acts as a unified search platform, combining metadata from all CLARIN centres and even extending to external repositories like Europeana.

A core part of CLARIN's infrastructure is its depositing service, enabling researchers to store resources such as corpora, lexicons, audio, video, and linguistic annotations. These resources are meticulously archived, with data held for extended periods (up to 50 years) and assigned persistent identifiers (PID) for reliable citations. Over 700,000 resources, representing numerous languages, are available in the VLO for cross-border data sharing and reuse, empowering scholars to leverage existing datasets rather than creating new ones from scratch.

Additional discovery tools like the Federated Content Search (FCS) and Language Resources Switchboard (SB) further enrich the exploration of data across CLARIN's distributed framework. By integrating metadata effectively, CLARIN ensures all resources and tools are accessible and searchable across its extensive infrastructure.

The CLARIN Resource Families initiative has the purpose of giving an overview of CLARIN resources domain by organising resources by type, language, and key metadata, thus offering user-friendly overviews and links to tutorials, relevant publications, and further training.

With these 4 points of access, CLARIN not only preserves essential language data but also promotes collaboration and innovation within the social sciences and digital humanities, aligning with open science goals and the FAIR data principles for transparency and accessibility across research disciplines.

2.3.1 Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)¹

The VLO constitutes the main CLARIN central discovery service, i.e. the principal means of finding and exploring Language Resources, broadly intended as both data and tools/services, which exploits the potential of CMDI metadata harvested from all the affiliated repositories. The use of shared CMDI metadata profiles for describing LRs allows for more easily findability of metadata in the VLO, because a central constant work is dedicated to refining the mapping of metadata onto VLO facets and to improve VLO functionalities. Many metadata formats are supported in the VLO: when a resource is deposited, its metadata goes through an automatic conversion process to CMDI format, so that all metadata coming from CLARIN resources becomes interoperable and comparable. This huge harmonisation effort of course comes at the cost of losing some specificity (that can still be maintained locally) and of a certain degree of fallacy. This is why periodic monitoring and metadata curation on the side of local repositories is also carried on, to ensure detailed and proper descriptions.

Early versions of VLO featured both a geographic exploration mode using a Google Earth overlay and a faceted browsing system. Over time, the geographic view was phased out,

¹ The VLO is accessible here: <https://vlo.clarin.eu/?1>.

while faceted browsing became the primary tool, evolving into the version seen today. This browsing approach categorizes resources by facets, such as language, country, and resource type, allowing users to refine their searches through a progressively filtered selection process. By selecting values within each facet, such as "French" for language or "Cameroon" for country, users can gain a clearer view of the available resource landscape and understand specific patterns across categories.

In addition to faceted browsing, VLO also integrates a free-text search function, letting users conduct both broad and targeted queries. This design combines ease of exploration with depth, supporting users who want either an overview of resources or a detailed look at specific types of data.

Figure 1: CLARIN VLO with its facets and search functions.

There are 12 different metadata, plus two other useful facets, that can be selected in order to narrow down the selection of displayed records:

1. **Language:** the object language relevant for the resource or tool;
2. **Collection:** the collection to which the resource or tool belongs;
3. **Resource Type:** the type of the language resource (e.g. tool, lexicon, grammar, corpus);
4. **Modality:** the modality of the content of the resource or intended for the tool (e.g. spoken or speech);
5. **File type:** the mime type used in the resource or by the tool;
6. **Keyword:** keywords describing the resource or tool;
7. **Genre:** the genre of the content of the resource (e.g. narrative or conversation);
8. **Subject:** the subject or topic of the content of the resource;
9. **Country:** the country of origin of the source material of the resource;

- 10. **Organisation:** the organisation currently responsible for the resource or tool, i.e. the holder of distribution rights;
- 11. **Metadata provider:** the repository in which the resource is actually deposited and that makes it available;
- 12. **National project:** the CLARIN national consortium to which the resource pertains.

Figure 2: The 12 metadata search filters, to the left, and some of the language options, to the right.

Two additional facets allow to select resources that cover a specific year range or that comes with a certain type of use and distribution licenses.

Figure 3: The 2 additional search filters for temporal coverage and availability.

2.3.2 Federated Content Search (FCS)²

Most textual and corpus resources hosted by CLARIN centres can be searched and inspected via dedicated query interfaces or applications run by the centres themselves or by the institutions that own the resources. However, such search interfaces are not always easily usable by first-time users as a vast array of query languages and different implementations can be found, which require time and effort to be learned. In order to spare researchers from learning several new query languages before even being certain that a certain resource actually meets their needs, CLARIN offers a Federated Content Search (FCS) service, that is an integrated search facility to make these unrelated and partly overlapping content search engines available to the research community from one single point of access and by using a common syntax. FCS enables a user to enter a single query that is sent simultaneously to multiple search engines at different federated CLARIN centres, which in turn search in the corpora they host. FCS therefore gives users the possibility to conduct a full-text search across all federated resources, or a selection of them. FCS is thus thought of as a first-level exploration of CLARIN corpora and textual data, which allows the identification of relevant resources.

The FCS approach differs from the metadata search, for example as performed in the VLO, where all metadata is first harvested (copied to a single server) and then centrally indexed. This is for several reasons:

- Legal issues make it impossible for some resources to be copied to another location;
- The size of many datasets makes decentralised indexing the most viable option;
- Most language resources are annotated in a collection-specific manner, which makes it hard to use or develop one single search engine that can cope with all of them.

Although more scalable, FCS comes at the cost of being less powerful than a local search and certain features are absent, such as ranking. FCS is therefore particularly useful as a first

The screenshot shows the CLARIN Content Search interface. At the top, there are navigation links: 'Content Search', 'Aggregatore', and 'Help'. The search bar is labeled 'Text layer CQL query' and contains the text 'farfalla'. Below the search bar, there are filters: 'Search for Any Language' (dropdown), 'Text layer Contextual Query Language (CQL)' (dropdown), 'in 527 selected resources' (dropdown), and 'and show up to 10 hits per endpoint' (input field). Below the search bar, it says '19 matching resources found in 524 searched resources'. There are two checkboxes: 'Show warnings and errors' and 'Display as Key Word In Context'. The first result is from 'Tagesspiegel' and contains text about 'Farfalla'.

Figure 4: An example of search in the FCS page: for the word "farfalla", 19 matching resources are found and listed below.

² The FCS is accessible here: <https://contentsearch.clarin.eu/>.

step to discover where interesting language resources are hosted and at which centre(s) a more specialised search could be useful.

2.3.3 Language Resource Switchboard (LRS)³

Many of the resources that can be discovered through the VLO can be used in many ways. On the one hand, a user can directly download the resources from the local CLARIN repository where these are stored and analyse them offline with their own preferred tools. On the other hand, these resources may be fit to be processed directly by CLARIN tools and services which are available online and distributed over various technical centres in Europe. CLARIN has streamlined this process, thus allowing the users to easily access tools that can be applied to a specific resource by immediately selecting it from the VLO or by using a specific tool: the Language Resource Switchboard (LRS). LRS therefore is a tool that helps a user find a matching language processing web application for a given resource and process it directly.

The screenshot displays the VLO interface for a record titled "Fairy legends and traditions of the South of Ireland". The record details section shows a table of resources:

Name	Type
_Resource_79121285	landing page
79121292.30.jpg	JPEG Image
79121288.23.pdf	PDF
79121285	HTML

A button "Process with Language Resource Switchboard" is located below the table. The LRS interface below shows the "Resources" section with a dropdown menu for "Extracted Text" (13.38 KiB) and a "Matching Tools" section. The tools listed include "WebLicht Const Parsing EN" and "UDPipe".

Figure 5: When searching for a specific resource in the VLO, a contextual menu lets the user choose to analyse the resource with LRS (figure above): by selecting "Process with Language Resources Switchboard", a list of all suitable tools for that resource is given in a dedicated page (figure below).

³ The LRS is accessible here: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/>.

Figure 6: This is an example of results given by Voyant Tools, that show vocabulary, token frequencies and many other text statistics.

2.3.4 CLARIN Resource Families⁴

The CLARIN Resource Families provide a user-friendly overview per resource type of the available language resources in the CLARIN infrastructure for researchers from the digital humanities, social sciences and human language technologies. The overviews are meant to facilitate comparative research, and the listings are sorted by language.

The listings for each family include the most important metadata as well as brief descriptions, such as resource size, text sources, time periods, annotations and licences, as well as links to download pages and concordancers. In addition to the resources found in the CLARIN infrastructure, an overview of other existing valuable language resources, which have not yet been integrated into the infrastructure, is provided.

Table 1: Here is a list of the CLARIN Resource Families that are currently gathered.

FAMILY TYPE	RESOURCE FAMILIES
Corpora	Computer-Mediated Communication Corpora Corpora of Academic Texts Corpora of Disordered Speech Historical Corpora L2 Learner Corpora

⁴ The overview of CLARIN Resource Families is available here: <https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families>.

	<p>Legal Corpora Literary Corpora Manually Annotated Corpora Multimodal Corpora Newspaper Corpora Oral History Corpora Parallel Corpora Parliamentary Corpora Reference Corpora Sign Language Resources Spoken Corpora Lexical Resources</p>
Lexical Resources	<p>Conceptual Resources Dictionaries Glossaries Language Models Lexica Wordlists</p>
Tools	<p>Corpus Query Tools Normalisation Named Entity Recognition Part-of-Speech Tagging and Lemmatisation Tools for Sentiment Analysis</p>

Literary corpora in the CLARIN infrastructure

Monolingual corpora

Corpus	Language	Description	Availability
<p>One-million Corpus of Croatian Literary Language</p> <p>Size: 1 million tokens</p>	Croatian	The corpus is listed in the LINDAT repository.	
<p>Johannes V. Jensen Corpus</p> <p>Size: 1,760,093 words, 8,489 pages Annotation: unannotated Licence: CC BY-SA 4.0</p>	Danish	<p>This corpus presents the collected works of the Danish author Johannes Jensen.</p> <p>The corpus is available for download from CLARIN-DK and for online browsing through a dedicated concordancer.</p>	<p>Browse</p> <p>Download</p>
<p>Complete Corpus</p>	English	This corpus is available for online browsing	Browse

Figure 7: For the literary corpora family, CLARIN Resource Families show a list of the main resources that fall under this definition.

3. CLARIN Semantic Framework

The Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI) is essential to the CLARIN ecosystem, providing a common semantic framework that supports interoperability, continuity, and the detailed description of language resources. CMDI addresses the challenges of metadata modeling, authoring, and harvesting by offering a flexible, component-based approach that allows users to create tailored metadata schemas. This adaptability ensures CMDI can meet the diverse needs of projects in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), while maintaining a standardized structure that promotes seamless integration.

Two key processes, metadata creation and metadata harvesting, are central to CMDI's effectiveness. Metadata creation involves generating accurate, detailed descriptions that enhance resource discoverability, while metadata harvesting consolidates these descriptions, enabling efficient and unified access across the CLARIN infrastructure. Together, these processes ensure semantic interoperability, allowing resources to be reused, combined, and accessed consistently across disciplines. Links to the CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR) further reinforce this semantic alignment, ensuring continuity and coherence in metadata descriptions across projects. The CMDI Component Registry and toolkit play a vital role in maintaining this shared metadata environment, supporting researchers by providing a rich, interoperable, and cohesive resource ecosystem.

This section also reviews the variety of language resources within CLARIN, providing examples of CMDI descriptions to illustrate how these metadata standards apply to real-world resources. Examples include corpora, lexical resources, and language processing tools, each demonstrating CMDI's capacity to capture detailed, standardized descriptions that support efficient discovery and reuse across the CLARIN infrastructure.

3.1 Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI)

CLARIN offers a solution for the modelling, authoring and exploitation of metadata. This solution is implemented as a set of standards, registries, definitions and workflows which together form the Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI).

CMDI was developed within the European CLARIN infrastructure, drawing from a range of expert input to establish a flexible metadata framework tailored to the diverse resources that emerged during CLARIN's preparatory phase in 2007. This flexibility became essential for accurately describing various resources across the infrastructure. Version 1.0 introduced the CMDI toolkit, including XML schemas and XSLT stylesheets to validate and transform metadata components, profiles, and records. The subsequent release, version 1.1, provided minor updates that foster the development of numerous tools and systems reliant on CMDI's standardized syntax and semantics. Currently, version 1.2 further extends CMDI's functionality, addressing issues and adding new features, with the support of an updated CMDI toolkit to facilitate the transition.

The original core requirements for CMDI in terms of features available to its users were that:

- Users must be able to create and use their own schema tailored specifically towards the requirements of their project.
- Users must be able to use the terminology that the specific (sub-)community is used to.
- Users must be able to mix vocabularies from various initiatives such as to extend and adapt the metadata schema to the needs of their project.

CMDI was designed to offer the advantages of shared conventions, common semantics and predefined structures while maintaining the flexibility required to serve the needs of CLARIN's core communities. The essential aim of the initiators of CMDI was to unite the above requirements, which reflect and address the heterogeneous nature of the metadata landscape with a high degree of interoperability and reusability, both within and across communities. What they proposed was a Component-based metadata infrastructure, revolving around a basic meta-model with Components and Profiles as its main entities, and concept links as the key to interoperability.

CMDI is a hierarchical metadata framework where a profile – from which an XML-based schema can be derived from – is built from smaller building blocks, CMDI components. Strictly speaking, the CMD model itself provides a solution for metadata modelling. Its direct users are metadata modellers, not metadata creators or other “end users”. The result of the metadata modelling process is a Profile. Such a profile acts as a complete blueprint for a metadata record, a document that describes one or more aspects of a resource. A record, which is per definition derived from one Profile, is often referred to as an instance of that Profile. Both the syntax and the semantics of a metadata record are defined in the Profile, which thus provides all necessary information for either creating a “valid” instance, or to interpret and verify the content of an existing CMD metadata record.

Figure 8: This picture shows the relationships between Profiles, Components and Attributes, thus giving an oversight on how CMDI is structured.

In contrast to metadata standards that are based on a single predefined schema or a small set of such schemas, Component Metadata (CMD) builds on an open-ended set of definitions. Components can be composed out of other components as well as more atomic, non-reusable constituent parts, namely Elements and Attributes. At various levels within these definitions, links to entries from the CLARIN Concept Registry are included, providing semantic robustness through common identifiers and definitions for shared concepts.

A CMDI metadata Record typically describes a single resource or a specific set of resources. There are multiple ways of authoring Records. Each Record, however, must be based on a single Profile. The Profile dictates the structure of the Record and specifies the scope and semantics of the values that it may contain. A Record is created as a single XML file. All CMDI records are structured in the same way, including a mandatory header and resource references section on top. The remainder of the record is formed by a section that follows a blueprint defined by a specific Profile, which may therefore differ between CMDI records.

The XML-CMDI that describes each resource is made up of two main sections: the header section and the components section. The header section contains some general indications about the Profile or the Components included and linked in the schema; the components section is made up of all the chosen Components, that contain the instances relative to the resource that is being described.

Annales veteres Veronenses

Press **ctrl + c** to copy

```
<cmd:CMD xmlns:cmd="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/" xmlns:lindat="http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/ns/experimental/cmd" xmlns:olac="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/" xmlns:ms="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" CMDVersion="1.1" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/ http://catalog.clarin.eu/ds/ComponentRegistry/rest/registry/profiles/clarin.eu:cr1:p_1403526079380/xsd">
  <cmd:Header>
    <cmd:MdCreationDate>2020-07-31</cmd:MdCreationDate>
    <cmd:MdSelfLink>https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/OPEN-136@format=cmdi</cmd:MdSelfLink>
    <cmd:MdProfile>clarin.eu:cr1:p_1403526079380</cmd:MdProfile>
    <cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName>ALIM Literary Sources</cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName>
  </cmd:Header>
  <cmd:Resources>
    <cmd:ResourceProxyList>
      <cmd:ResourceProxy id="lp_173">
        <cmd:ResourceType>LandingPage</cmd:ResourceType>
      </cmd:ResourceProxy>
    </cmd:ResourceProxyList>
  </cmd:Resources>
</cmd:CMD>
```

Figure 9: This is an example of a CMDI record of a literary corpus. The opening part of the record, namely the header, contains all the necessary references and specifications, giving a first glance at the resource itself.

A list of all the Components and Profiles comprised in the CMDI infrastructure is available in the CMDI Component Registry⁵: the Component Registry offers a comprehensive descriptions of all the available Profiles and associated Components, also giving the appropriate reference to the concepts stored in the CLARIN Concept Registry. The Component Registry is implemented as a web service that exposes a set of paths that represent various sub-registries based on the common representational state transfer

⁵ CMDI Component Registry is accessible here: <https://catalog.clarin.eu/ds/ComponentRegistry/#/>.

(REST) principles: clients can perform “create”, “read”, “update”, and “delete” operations on individual items – Component and Profile definitions – and use additional commands

Name	Group Name	Domain Name	Creator	Description	Registrati...	Com...
AnnotatedCorpusProfile-DLU	DLU		GrietDepoorter	A CMDI profile for ...	2013-10-24	0
AnnotationTool			Eric Sanders	Description of a to...	2011-02-09	0
ArthurianFiction		Other	Rik Hoekstra	Profile for Arthuria...	2012-09-04	0
BamdesLexicalResource		Computational ...	Dieter Van Uytv...	Lexical Resource a...	2010-10-27	0
BamdesMultimodalCorpus		Computational ...	Dieter Van Uytv...	Oral Corpus as use...	2010-10-27	0
BamdesOralCorpus		Computational ...	Dieter Van Uytv...	Oral Corpus as use...	2010-10-27	0
BamdesTool		Computational ...	Dieter Van Uytv...	Tool as used by BA...	2010-10-27	0
BamdesWrittenCorpus		Computational ...	Dieter Van Uytv...	Written Corpus as ...	2010-10-27	0
BASWebService	CLARIN-D Versi...	Phonetics	71A3DD8C90E8...	This is a derived w...	2015-03-11	0

Figure 10: The CMDI Component Registry shows a list of all available Components, and dedicated facets allow for searching, editing and filtering Components.

with respect to the lifecycle stage of items under their control.

The typical lifecycle of an item (Component or Profile) is as follows:

- A user defines an item and registers it in their personal registry (also called a workspace).
- The user optionally performs one or more updates to the item definition.
- The item gets published in the public registry, making it available to others for use or reuse.
- The item may at a certain point be marked as deprecated, which means its status changes, and from there on its use is discouraged by the application; however, the item will never be deleted once published. Until publication, an item can only be used or reused by its owner, which may be a single user or a defined group of users (called a “Team” in the Component Registry).

A crucial responsibility of the Component Registry is to serve formal schemas for individual profiles that can be also used for validation.

In CLARIN's central infrastructure, metadata records are regularly aggregated from multiple sources such as CLARIN centres, after which they are semantically aligned and finally indexed to make the described resources discoverable in a uniform way. Many other possible ways of using CMDI metadata exist for a variety of purposes. Some use cases for CMDI metadata exploitation are ingestion, aggregation, conversion, search and discovery.

3.2 CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR)⁶

The CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR) forms the basis of the semantic interoperability layer of CLARIN, especially in the context of metadata in CMDI format. It does so by offering a collection of Concepts, identifiable by their persistent identifiers, relevant for the domain of language resources; each of these Concepts can be referenced by a related Profile or Component that is archived in the CMDI Component Registry.

Figure 11: Each metadata record is derived from a Profile, that is linked to a concept and its persistent identifier, that are stored in the CLARIN Concept Registry.

The Concept Registry can be accessed by anyone using a read-only faceted browser or via the search facilities of the CMDI Component Registry. Adding new concepts or changing existing ones can only be done by the national CCR coordinators. In case someone needs to add or change a concept, it is possible to contact their national CCR coordinators and ask for assistance.

The screenshot shows the 'CCR: CLARIN Concept Registry' interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Content language English' and a search box. The main content area is divided into two sections: 'Vocabulary information' and a list of concepts.

Vocabulary information

TITLE: CCR: CLARIN Concept Registry
 TYPE: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme>
 URI: http://hdl.handle.net/11459/CCR_P-Metadata_6f3f84d1-6f06-6291-4e20-4cd361cca128

Resource counts by type

Type	Count
Concept	3079
- Deprecated concept	0
Collection	51

Term counts by language

Language	Preferred terms	Alternate terms	Hidden terms
English	3079	176	11

The left sidebar shows a list of concepts under 'Alphabetical' sorting, including terms like 'aant_bladen', 'aantal', 'aantal_lied', etc.

Figure 12: The CCR offers a comprehensive list of all concepts available; for each concept, a persistent identifier is given.

⁶ CCR is accessible here: <https://vocabularies.clarin.eu/clavas/ccr/en/>.

In the past the concept registry role was taken by ISOcat, which was the ISO TC37 Data Category Registry (DCR) created in 2008 as one of the first ISO standards delivered in the form of a database (ISOcat). The Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics (MPI) has provided development, hosting, and support services and acted as the Registration Authority (RA) for ISOcat. The use of the DCR by various communities, including CLARIN, has grown over the years. Feedback from users, coupled with changes in ISO standardisation procedures, necessitated a review of the system and operational framework with an aim towards improving usability. In line with these insights and MPI's renewed focus on institute research, the MPI stopped being the RA and hosting provider in December 2014. For CLARIN users the Meertens Institute hosts the new CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR). This registry contains the relevant concepts (based on the corresponding ISOcat data categories), such as those used by CMDI. The CCR has a less complex data model than ISOcat, and is also a closed registry, i.e., only the national CCR-coordinators are able to input and edit (new) concepts.

The screenshot shows the termweb4 interface. At the top, it displays the dictionary name 'ASTM F43 (2023) (0 of 1 section)', source 'English', target 'English', and filter 'No filter'. A search bar on the left contains 'corpus (plural corpora)'. The main content area shows a concept entry for 'corpus (plural corpora)' with a Concept ID of 149. The entry details are as follows:

Dictionary	ASTM F43 (2023)
Section	Published Terms
Definition	a collection of naturally occurring language samples compiled as written texts or as a transcription of recorded speech stored electronically.
Source	1562

Below the definition, there is a section for 'English' with a right-pointing arrow, and the term 'corpus (plural corpora)' is listed again.

Figure 13: The ISOcat for "corpus" comprises a ConceptID and a definition, thus allowing a transparent formalisation for the linked concept in CCR.

The CCR has become the de facto standard for CMDI metadata designers when referencing data category definitions. However, the CMDI specification does not require the use of CCR, as it supports any term registry (or semantic registry) that can establish a shared vocabulary across CMDI components and profiles. Therefore, CMDI promotes semantic interoperability within the CLARIN ecosystem by prioritizing the CCR as a common reference across profiles. As a result, CMDI-based profiles (and their XML-based schemas) typically share a substantial portion of their vocabulary. Most CMDI profiles rely exclusively on the CCR, and therefore are not directly linked to external data sources beyond CLARIN.

CMDI Component Registry Login help

Public space Profiles [Filter] + New Edit as new Delete Status Type to filter... Showing 184 of 184

Name	Group Name	Domain Name	Creator	Description	Registrati...	Com...
LCC_SentenceProfile	informatik.uni-le...	Text and Corpus ...	Thomas Eckart	Describes a sentenc...	2018-03-23	0
LESLLA	DCS/LESLLA		vdelint	CMDI metadata prof...	2013-08-14	0
LINDAT_CLARIN			Ondrej Kosarko	profile used for LIN...	2015-10-22	0
LexicalResourceProfile	NaLiDa		nalida	A CMDI profile for le...	2019-10-31	0
LexicalResourceProfile			Laura van Eerten	a profile for describ...	2010-04-26	2
LexicalResourceProfile-DLU	DLU		GrietDepoorter	a profile for describ...	2013-09-26	0
LexicalResourceProfile-DLU	DLU		GrietDepoorter	a profile for describ...	2013-12-27	0

view xml Comments (0)

Component: LexicalResourceContext

"A component for describing, for instance, the type, subject languages, modality and headword type of a lexical resource."

Number of occurrences: 1 - 1

Element: LexiconType

Value scheme: string
 ConceptLink: http://hdl.handle.net/11459/CCR_C-2487_472ad387-0b4e-3782-cb65-be9b20cb656d
 DisplayPriority: 1
 Number of occurrences: 0 - unbounded

CCR: CLARIN Concept Registry Content language English Search

Alphabetical Hierarchy Groups

- Dialogue Acts
- Language Codes
- Language Resource Ontology
- Lexical Resources
- Lexical Semantics
- Lexicography
- Metadata
 - lexiconType lexicon type**
 - Morphosyntax
 - Multilingual Information Management
 - not available
 - Semantic Content Representation
 - Sign Language
 - Syntax
 - Terminology
 - Translation
 - undecided

lexiconType lexicon type

PREFERRED TERM **lexiconType lexicon type**

DEFINITION A description of the type of the lexicon. (source: CLARIN)

ENTRY TERMS *lexiconType*

BELONGS TO GROUP **Metadata**

CHANGE NOTE This concept is based on the ISOcat data category: <http://www.isocat.org/datcat/DC-2487>

EXAMPLE bilingual dictionary (source: CLARIN)
 glossary term base (source: CLARIN)
 monolingual dictionary (source: CLARIN)
 thesaurus (source: CLARIN)
 word list (source: CLARIN)

NOTATION *lexiconType*

IN OTHER LANGUAGES *lexiconType*

URI http://hdl.handle.net/11459/CCR_C-2487_472ad387-0b4e-3782-cb65-

Figure 14: When selecting a profile in CMDI Component Registry, the user is given an overview of all its Components (picture above); each Component can be linked to an entry in CCR, that gives an accurate definition and a hierarchical presentation (picture below).

3.3 Metadata creation and metadata harvesting

Metadata creation and harvesting are essential processes that ensure interoperability, accessibility, and usability within the CLARIN infrastructure. Metadata creation involves a structured process that includes login, template selection, item description, and automatic metadata generation, using CMDI standards to make resources easily discoverable and reusable. Examples from ILC4CLARIN will illustrate these steps in action. Metadata retrieval allows researchers to locate resources via the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) and Federated Content Search (FCS), which use standardized protocols for metadata harvesting. By streamlining metadata creation and retrieval, CLARIN builds an interoperable framework that promotes efficient resource discovery and reuse within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) community.

3.3.1 How metadata is created

When depositing a resource in a CLARIN repository, the system generates a CMDI record to describe the resource accurately for easy discovery, sharing, and reuse. This metadata creation process follows a structured approach that is easy-to-use and immediate for the users of the SSH field. The depositing process⁷ established for ILC4CLARIN repository will be described in this paragraph, as an example of how metadata is created in the CLARIN Semantic Framework.

1. Login with Federated Account

Before the depositing process starts, a login with an account coming from a recognized account provider is required, following the Single Sign-On (SSO) indications.

Figure 15: Login facet to ILC4CLARIN repository.

⁷ The tutorial on how to deposit a resource on ILC4CLARIN repository is available at this link: <https://dspace-clarin-it.ilc.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/page/deposit#>

2. Template Selection

CLARIN uses metadata templates designed for different data types and disciplines, ensuring the metadata aligns with the resource's characteristics, so the system first asks the user to specify the data type of the resource that will be deposited.

Figure 16: ILC4CLARIN offers 4 different resource profiles, corresponding to a specific metadata schema.

3. Item description

The chosen template automatically leads the user to the right facets that are best suited to describe the resource, starting with the specification of people and organisations involved in the creation of the resource.

The screenshot shows the 'Item submission' process with a progress bar from 1 to 8. Steps 1 through 7 are marked with green checkmarks, and step 2, 'Who's involved', is highlighted. Below the progress bar is the 'People and organizations involved' facet. It contains two sections: 'Authors' and 'Publisher'. The 'Authors' section has two input fields: 'Last name, e.g. Smith' and 'First name(s) + "Jr", e.g. Donald Jr', each with an 'Add' button below it. The 'Publisher' section has one input field with an 'Add' button below it. Below the input fields is a small information box with an 'i' icon and text: 'Enter the names of the authors of this item. Start typing the author's last name and use autocomplete form that will appear if applicable. End your input by pressing ESC if you don't want to use the preselected value.'

Figure 17: This is the facet for the fields that explicit authors, publishers and other people or organisations involved in the creation and distribution of the resource.

Contact person

Contact person's given name

Contact person's surname

Contact person's email

Contact person's institution name

 Person to contact in case of any issues with this submission.

Funding

Funding organization

Grant no. or funding project code

Funding project name

Funding type

 Acknowledge sponsors and funding that supported work described by this submission. In case your submission is suitable for OpenAIRE, describe it in the "Note" step of this submission.

Figure 18: Following from Figure 17, in this facet other important roles and authorities can be explicated.

After that, a description of the main characteristics of the resource is asked.

Basic Info Who's involved **3. Describe** 4. Upload 5. License 6. Note 7. Review 8. Complete

Resource details

Description

i Enter a description of the submitted data.

Language

Add

i Select the language of the main content of the item. Multiple languages are possible. Start typing the language and use autocomplete form that will appear if applicable.

Subject Keywords

Add

i Enter appropriate subject keyword or phrase and press the Add button. You can repeat it for multiple keywords or use separators i.e., comma and semicolon, which will split it accordingly. Start typing the keyword and use autocomplete form that will appear. End your input by pressing ESC if you don't want to use the preselected value.

Size

Unit

Add

i You can state the extent of the submitted data, eg. the number of tokens.

Media type

i Media type of the main content of the item e.g., "text" for textual corpora or "audio" for audio recordings.

< Previous Save & Exit Next >

Figure 19: In this facet the main characteristics of the resource can be described, such as a short description, the language used in the resource, a list of keywords, the size with different kinds of units for measurement, and the media type.

At this point, the system asks for the files to be uploaded via a dedicated facet.

Item submission

Basic Info Who's involved Describe Upload License Note Review Complete

Upload File(s)

File

No file chosen

i Please enter the full path of the file on your computer corresponding to your item. If you click "Browse...", a new window will allow you to select the file from your computer.

When uploading language resources, please try to use one of the recommended formats mentioned in [LRT Standards](#)

Uploading **files larger than** requires special handling. Please contact [Help Desk](#) about how to upload these files. Thank you for your understanding.

Drop file(s) here.

Please note, that you can select licences in the License step of this submission after you upload at least one file.

Figure 20: In this field the upload of the resource can be performed.

The last thing that the user is asked is to accept a Distribution License Agreement and to specify the distribution and use licenses intended for the resource.

Basic Info Who's involved Describe Upload License Note Review Complete

Read and accept the [Distribution License Agreement](#)

Click to accept By checking this box, you agree to the Distribution License Agreement for this repository to reproduce, translate and distribute your submissions worldwide.

! If you have questions regarding this licence please contact the [Help Desk](#).

Figure 21: Distribution License Agreement with ILC4CLARIN repository.

Figure 22: From a precompiled list, the user can choose the suitable distribution and usage license.

4. Automatic Metadata Generation

Certain metadata fields, such as the depositor's information or the date, are automatically filled by the repository: the information about the depositor is deduced by the federated login and the user's identity provider.

5. Metadata Storage and Search Optimization

Once finalized, the CMDI metadata is indexed, enabling advanced search and discovery features across i.e. the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO). This indexation facilitates access for researchers looking for specific language resources across CLARIN's network.

This metadata creation process ensures that resources deposited in CLARIN repositories are well-documented, easily searchable, and highly interoperable across different digital infrastructures.

3.3.2 How metadata is retrieved

In CLARIN, metadata harvesting is conducted through the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) and Federated Content Search (FCS), using the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Repositories connected to CLARIN expose metadata in CMDI (Component Metadata Infrastructure) format, which is compatible with CLARIN's standards for interoperability. The harvested metadata undergoes mapping and processing, aligning with a unified schema to enhance searchability and standardization. This process allows users to perform both metadata-based and full-text searches, ensuring resources are accurately indexed and accessible across CLARIN's digital infrastructure.

Figure 23: The metadata describing the language resources hosted on a CLARIN repository is exposed in CMDI format for easy harvesting by the VLO and the FCS.

This harmonized CMDI schema allows for consistency in metadata presentation across resources, ensuring users can seamlessly search by relevant fields, such as language, resource type, modality, or genre. By indexing the metadata into a single, centralized interface, CLARIN supports both browsing and advanced search functionalities, helping users quickly locate resources that meet their specific research needs. Additionally, VLO enhances searchability through faceted browsing, enabling researchers to refine results based on various criteria and make direct comparisons between similar resources. The

indexed metadata also expose the key features that allow immediate selection of suitable tools for linguistic analysis through the LRS.

Figure 24: The harvested metadata is used to compile results for search queries in the VLO, and also to find matching tools in LRS.

The screenshot shows the VLO interface for a search record titled "SmartKom Audio". The record details are as follows:

- Name:** SmartKom Audio
- Description:** This corpus contains the audio recordings of all actors who use the SmartKom system; it covers the audio recordings (no video) and annotations of all three original SmartKom corpora Public, Mobile and Home. Naive users were asked to test a 'prototype' for a market study not knowing that the system was in fact controlled by two human operators. They were asked to solve two tasks in a period of 4,5 min while they were left alone with the system. The instruction was kept to a minimum; in fact the user only knew that the system is able to understand speech, gestures and even mimical expressions and should more or less communicate like a human. Man-Machine-Interaction by coordinated analysis and generation of multiple models.
- Collection:** Bavarian Archive for Speech Signals (BAS)
- Language:** German, English
- Modality:** spoken, emotional-state
- Continent:** Europe
- Country:** Germany
- Genre:** multi-modal wizard-of-oz recordings of human - machine dialogues
- Subject:** multi-modal wizard-of-oz recordings of human - machine dialogues
- Organisation:** Bavarian Archive for Speech Signals, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universitaet Muenchen

Additional features shown include a "Landing page" button, a "Linked resource" section with a document icon labeled "doc_SKAUDIO.zip", and a "Linked records" section showing "447 children".

Figure 25: Here is an example of metadata presentation that was taken from a search record in the VLO.

The VLO's design goes beyond simple metadata aggregation; it aims to provide a user-centred experience, offering researchers intuitive pathways to a vast and diverse catalogue of resources.

3.4 CLARIN resource types: Language and Text Resources description

CLARIN is focused on providing access to all kinds of language resources for all the researchers in the SSH field and beyond. Thanks to the overview offered by CLARIN Resource Families, it is possible to extract a detailed list of all the language resources that CLARIN hosts on its repositories and makes findable and accessible via the VLO and through the FCS: such a list can pave the way for the formalisation of the CLARIN domain ontology.

CLARIN linguistic resources are mainly divided into two categories: on the one hand, the Datasets category comprises all kinds of texts in all kinds of modality, including lexical resources that may include annotations and linguistic analysis; on the other hand, the Tools category comprises all the tools and technologies that can be used to carry out linguistic analysis i.e. on morphological, syntactical or semantic levels.

3.4.1 Datasets

CORPORA

A corpus is a large and structured collection of texts or spoken language samples that are systematically compiled and organized for linguistic analysis. These texts can be in written form (such as books, newspapers, or web content) or transcribed from spoken language (such as conversations, interviews, or broadcast speech). Corpora are used in linguistics, natural language processing (NLP), and other language-related fields to study various aspects of language, such as grammar, vocabulary, semantics, and discourse.

Some key features of corpora are:

- **Size and Structure:** A corpus is usually large and carefully structured to represent a language or a particular variety of language (e.g., academic texts, casual conversations, or historical documents).
- **Representativeness:** A corpus is designed to be representative of a particular language, dialect, register, or domain to allow generalizable conclusions about language use.
- **Annotations:** Corpora are often annotated with additional linguistic information, such as part-of-speech tags, syntactic structures, semantic roles, or prosody features. These annotations enrich the corpus for more detailed linguistic analysis.
- **Format:** Modern corpora are typically created in electronic format, allowing for automated searches and computational analysis using specialized software; older resources often undergo a process of digitalisation in order to allow for further computational analysis and treatments.

Corpora can be categorized according to their composition and purpose. Here is a non-comprehensive list of different kinds of corpora hosted on CLARIN repositories, as enumerated in CLARIN Resource Families.

1. Computer-Mediated Communication Corpora (CMC Corpora)

Computer-mediated communication (CMC) constitutes public and private communication online, for instance blogs and forums, comments on online news sites, social media and networking sites such as Twitter and Facebook, or mobile phone applications such as WhatsApp, email and chat rooms. Because corpora that compile computer-mediated communication often include very informal styles of writing, they are interesting for a wide range of research fields, such as language variation, pragmatics, media and communication studies, etc. They are also important for the development of robust tools that can deal with non-standard spelling, vocabulary and grammar. The compilation and dissemination of such corpora are hindered by the unclear legal status of CMC data when distributed as a resource to the scientific community, as well as rapidly changing terms of service by content providers.

2. Corpora of Academic Texts

Corpora of academic texts contain scholarly writing, such as research papers, essays, and abstracts published in academic journals, conference proceedings, and edited volumes, as well as theses and dissertations written by students at undergraduate and graduate levels. They may also include scientific monographs, textbooks, lecture notes, and other materials used in academic settings. These corpora are essential for studying formal academic language, disciplinary discourse, argumentation structures, citation practices, and the use of specialized terminology across various fields. They are also valuable for analysing the linguistic differences between novice and expert writers, understanding how academic writing evolves over time, and developing tools for academic writing support, such as grammar checkers and plagiarism detection systems. Additionally, they can be used in comparative studies of academic writing across languages and cultures.

3. Corpora of Disordered Speech

Corpora for Speech with Disorders focus on speech data from individuals with communication disorders (CSD). These corpora are invaluable for research and education, though they are costly to create and difficult to share due to concerns about privacy, confidentiality, and the effort required to prepare datasets for standardized sharing. Despite these challenges, sharing such data enhances the reproducibility of research, facilitates systematic reviews, and allows other researchers to pursue new questions. Pooling comparable datasets enables more sophisticated analyses, supports cross-linguistic research, and is particularly useful for studying rare conditions. By encouraging the sharing of speech data from individuals with CSD, these corpora aim to advance clinical linguistics, phonetics, and speech therapy research, fostering collaboration and maximizing the impact of collected data.

4. Historical Corpora

Historical corpora are collections of texts from earlier periods of a language, often spanning several centuries, which are used to study the evolution of language over time. These

corpora include a wide range of written materials, such as legal documents, literary works, letters, and newspapers, allowing researchers to analyse changes in grammar, vocabulary, orthography, and style across different historical contexts. Historical corpora provide valuable insights into how languages develop, adapt, and shift due to social, political, and cultural influences. They also enable diachronic linguistic studies, comparative analyses between modern and historical language stages, and the development of tools for processing historical texts in NLP. Given their importance, historical corpora contribute to fields such as historical linguistics, philology, and lexicography.

5. L2 Learner Corpora

L2 learner corpora play a crucial role in second language research and pedagogy, allowing for a systematic study of how learners acquire a new language at both lexical and syntactic levels, as well as how their native language influences this process. These corpora provide insights into common challenges learners face, including specific errors in vocabulary and grammar. A special characteristic of L2 learner corpora is the markup of errors, which categorizes different types of mistakes, helping educators identify areas that need more focus in instruction. Additionally, many learner corpora also include annotations of prosodic features, such as intonation and rhythm, which are important for understanding spoken language production. Overall, L2 learner corpora are essential for enhancing language teaching strategies and improving learner outcomes.

6. Legal Corpora

Legal corpora contain legislation, legal acts, transcriptions of court decisions, and other kinds of materials related to national or supranational law. Such corpora are an important resource for anyone who practises or researches law, as they can be used to investigate issues such as legal phraseology and terminology, variation in legal discourse, legal translation, register and genre perspectives on legal discourse, legal discourse in forensic contexts, and evaluative language in judicial settings.

7. Literary Corpora

Literary corpora encompass a diverse range of texts, including poetry and fictional prose, such as novels, short stories, and plays. These corpora can either compile the complete works of a single author or feature representative texts from specific literary periods, showcasing the evolution of literary styles and themes. By providing a structured collection of texts, literary corpora facilitate in-depth analysis of language, style, and narrative techniques used by different authors or within various literary movements. Additionally, because literary corpora are often accessible through advanced concordancers, they are particularly well-suited for both quantitative and qualitative approaches to comparative literary analysis. Researchers can conduct statistical analyses to identify patterns in language use, thematic elements, and stylistic features, while also engaging in close reading and interpretation of individual texts. This dual approach allows scholars to explore relationships within a single genre or across different genres and historical periods, contributing to a deeper understanding of literary development and cultural context. Furthermore, literary corpora can also support interdisciplinary studies, linking literature with fields such as linguistics, cultural studies, and history, thus enriching the overall discourse in literary scholarship.

8. Manually Annotated Corpora

Manual annotated corpora are collections of texts enriched with manually validated or assigned linguistic information, such as morphosyntactic tags, lemmas, syntactic parses, named entities, and more. These corpora are particularly valuable for ensuring the accuracy of linguistic data, as human annotation reduces the errors that can occur in automated processing. They serve a dual purpose: they can be used to train new language annotation tools by providing high-quality data for machine learning algorithms, and they can be employed to test and evaluate the performance of existing annotation tools, ensuring they function accurately across different linguistic contexts.

Manual corpora are typically classified into six categories based on the type of manual annotation they include:

- Part-of-Speech (PoS) and Morphosyntactic Descriptions (MSD) tagging;
- Lemmatization;
- Syntactic parsing;
- Named Entity Recognition (NER);
- Sentiment analysis;
- Other types of linguistic annotations.

When a corpus is manually annotated for more than one type of linguistic information, it is classified under all relevant sections, making it versatile for various research and development purposes. Manual corpora are invaluable in refining Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools and improving the precision of language technologies, as they provide a reliable gold standard against which automated systems can be tested and improved. Additionally, they play a critical role in linguistics research, enabling detailed analysis of linguistic structures and patterns.

9. Multimodal Corpora

Multimodal corpora are collections of data designed to study how different modes of communication, such as speech, gestures, and facial expressions, interact in human communication. Typically consisting of video and audio recordings with accompanying transcriptions and gesture annotations, these corpora allow researchers to analyse the interplay between verbal and non-verbal cues. Some multimodal corpora also include textual data paired with images, providing insights into visual and textual communication. These resources are essential for examining how lexical, prosodic (intonation, rhythm), and gestural elements combine in natural conversations, helping to advance research in fields like linguistics, conversation analysis, and communication studies. Additionally, they play a key role in developing technologies such as virtual assistants, gesture recognition systems, and human-computer interaction tools, as they offer real-world examples of how humans communicate across multiple channels.

10. Newspaper Corpora

Digital collections of newspapers provide an invaluable resource for researchers across various disciplines in the Humanities and Social Sciences. They offer a wealth of information for both synchronic and diachronic research. These collections are particularly useful in fields such as history, media and communication studies, sociology, and linguistics.

Newspapers capture a broad spectrum of societal issues, public opinion, and cultural shifts, making them essential for understanding historical contexts and media trends. For lexicography, newspapers are a key resource for studying language in use, offering insights into neologisms, slang, and other linguistic phenomena as they emerge and evolve over time. By tracing language changes and lexical innovations across decades or centuries, researchers can examine how social, political, and technological factors influence both language and communication practices. Furthermore, digital newspaper corpora allow for large-scale, computational analysis, enabling detailed investigations of linguistic patterns, discourse trends, and the development of new terminologies in real-time.

11. Oral History Corpora

Oral History corpora focus on speech data related to personal histories, typically gathered through first-person interviews. These interviews, often structured or semi-structured, capture unique personal and historical experiences, distinguishing them from standard social science interviews, because oral history interviews have a specific historical and personal character. This data is valuable for a wide range of disciplines, including sociolinguistics, media studies, computational linguistics, trauma studies, and psychology. Oral history research often involves converting audio into text for analysis, using dedicated transcription and annotation tools. This makes the data accessible for a variety of analytical methods across different fields. The interdisciplinary nature of oral history comes from its combination of voice, language, and memory, making it a rich resource for studies that examine human expression in various contexts. The insights drawn from these interviews offer new opportunities for research by merging principles from multiple domains.

12. Parallel Corpora

Parallel corpora play a vital role in translation studies and contrastive linguistics, as they consist of texts in two or more languages that are aligned at the sentence or phrase level. These corpora are essential for comparing linguistic structures across languages and understanding how concepts are expressed differently across cultures. Many parallel corpora are accessible via user-friendly concordancers, which make it easier to study interlinguistic phenomena, such as translation shifts and lexical equivalence. In addition to their significance in research, parallel corpora are an invaluable resource for language teaching, providing authentic examples of how ideas are translated and allowing students to compare translations with original texts. They are also crucial for the development of machine translation systems, especially as training data for statistical and neural machine translation models. By learning from parallel corpora, these systems improve their ability to produce accurate translations across different language pairs. Overall, parallel corpora contribute to both academic research and practical applications in language technology.

13. Parliamentary Corpora

Parliamentary corpora are a crucial multidisciplinary resource that offer valuable insights across a wide range of fields. These collections of parliamentary proceedings can be studied from perspectives including political science, sociology, history, psychology, and various linguistic applications, such as critical discourse analysis. The structured nature of

parliamentary debates makes them ideal for examining political rhetoric, decision-making processes, and the linguistic strategies used by politicians.

The widespread availability of digitized parliamentary proceedings, especially in EU countries where access to public information is legally supported, has fuelled numerous national and international initiatives to compile, process, and analyse these corpora. This has resulted in the creation of large-scale databases of parliamentary speech, which are useful for studying changes in political discourse over time, tracking the evolution of key policy debates, and analysing how language reflects ideological shifts. In linguistics, parliamentary corpora are used to explore phenomena such as language variation, persuasive strategies, and the dynamics of spoken political interactions. Additionally, they provide a rich resource for developing tools and technologies that assist in text analysis, speech recognition, and other language-related applications.

14. Reference Corpora

A reference corpus is designed to provide a comprehensive and wide-ranging representation of a language, serving as a standard for linguistic research. Unlike specialized corpora, such as parliamentary or computer-mediated communication (CMC) corpora, which focus on specific types of language use, reference corpora aim to cover a broad spectrum of genres. These typically include a diverse set of primarily written texts, such as fiction, journalism, academic writing, and technical documents, and may also include spoken language data.

The genre diversity of reference corpora makes them invaluable for a variety of linguistic studies, from lexicography and syntax to studies of language variation and change. They are also essential for developing language tools and resources, such as dictionaries and grammars, and for training natural language processing systems, as their wide coverage ensures the models are robust and adaptable across different text types. Due to their comprehensive scope, reference corpora are often seen as authoritative by the linguistic community, providing a reliable baseline for understanding the general use of a language.

15. Sign Language Resources

Sign language (SL) corpus resources are essential collections that contain detailed transcriptions and annotations of spontaneous or elicited dialogues and narratives produced by Deaf signers. Since sign languages are expressed through a gestural and spatial-visual modality, all SL corpora are provided in video format, capturing the full range of hand movements, facial expressions, and body postures that are integral to conveying meaning. For Deaf-blind signers, sign languages can also be received through tactile modalities, expanding the scope of SL corpora to include alternative methods of communication.

These resources are invaluable for a wide array of linguistic research areas, such as lexicography, phonology, syntax and pragmatics. SL corpora also contribute to language typology, helping researchers compare sign languages across different communities to better understand their unique characteristics and commonalities. Beyond linguistics, SL corpora are used to develop educational resources, promote sign language preservation, and improve technologies like sign language recognition and machine translation systems. They are vital for both academic research and the Deaf community, ensuring that sign languages are documented, studied, and respected as full and complex languages.

16. Spoken Corpora

Corpora of spoken language contain transcriptions of both spontaneous and planned speech, such as conversations, broadcast news, or elicited narratives and dialogues. These transcriptions are often aligned with the original audio or video recordings, preserving features like intonation and rhythm, which are crucial for analysing spoken language. Spoken corpora are invaluable for various types of linguistic research, including phonology, conversational analysis, and dialectology. They allow researchers to study sound patterns, how people interact in conversation, and regional language variations. These corpora are typically sampled carefully and include rich sociodemographic metadata, providing details about the speakers, such as age, gender, and geographic background. In addition to their linguistic value, spoken corpora are also used in fields like speech recognition technology and language education.

LEXICAL RESOURCES

1. Conceptual Resources

Conceptual resources, also known as concept-based resources, include onomasiological lexical tools such as wordnets, framenets, thesauri, and ontologies. These resources are structured around concepts rather than specific words and are typically interlinked through semantic relations, like hypernymy (general-to-specific) and hyponymy (specific-to-general). By organising words and meanings based on their conceptual relationships, these resources support linguistic research and language technology, providing a framework for understanding and analysing language in a more structured and semantically rich way.

2. Dictionaries

Dictionaries were primarily created for human use in various contexts such as language learning, teaching, translation, and lexicological research. They are typically semasiological, meaning they are organized around words and provide detailed information about each word's meanings, definitions, pronunciation, grammatical properties, and usage. In addition to these core functions, dictionaries often include other features such as etymology, synonyms, antonyms, and example sentences to help users better understand how words are used in context. While originally designed for manual consultation, many modern dictionaries have been adapted for digital use, enabling more efficient searches and integrations into language technologies.

3. Glossaries

Glossaries are specialized dictionaries that focus on domain-specific terminology and expressions used within a particular field or discipline. Unlike general dictionaries, which cover a wide range of everyday language, glossaries are tailored to the needs of professionals, students, and researchers working within a specific area, such as medicine, law, engineering, or finance. They provide concise definitions or explanations of terms that may not be widely known outside the field, often including relevant abbreviations, acronyms, or jargon. Glossaries are essential tools for ensuring clarity and precision in technical writing and communication, helping to standardize terminology and facilitate understanding within specialized domains.

4. Language Models

Language models are pretrained probabilistic models that predict the likelihood of word sequences. These models help determine the most natural or probable sequence of words in a given language, allowing tools trained on them to select the correct word order or structure. While basic language models assign probabilities to simple word sequences, more advanced models can handle complex linguistic structures. This makes them useful for a variety of tasks and implementation of tool functionalities such as morphosyntax, machine translation, syntactic parsing, named entity recognition, lemmatization, defining baseline models and generating contextual word embeddings for language processing.

5. Lexica

Lexica are primarily used in language processing applications and serve as essential resources for various computational tasks. They typically contain an extensive inventory of lexical items, providing detailed linguistic information such as morphosyntactic properties, semantic features, and sometimes sentiment analysis. These resources are crucial for applications like part-of-speech tagging, parsing, machine translation, and sentiment analysis, where understanding the grammatical and semantic roles of words is essential. In addition to morphosyntactic data, lexica may also include word frequency, collocations, and pronunciation, making them versatile tools for both NLP tasks and language research.

6. Wordlists

Wordlists are simple yet valuable lexical resources that provide inventories of words, typically organised either alphabetically or by frequency of occurrence. While they lack detailed linguistic information like grammatical categories or semantic relations, wordlists are essential for many linguistic and computational applications. For instance, they are used in tasks such as spell checking, language teaching, keyword extraction, and text analysis. Frequency-based wordlists are particularly useful for identifying the most common or relevant words in a specific language or corpus, which can inform curriculum design, vocabulary selection for learners, or even language modelling for NLP tasks. Although more basic than comprehensive lexica or dictionaries, wordlists play a foundational role in many fields of language study and technology.

3.4.2 Tools

1. Corpus Query Tools

Corpus Query Tools are software applications that facilitate the searching, exploration, analysis, and visualization of linguistic corpora and texts, which are essential to digital scholarship in the humanities and social sciences. A wide range of such tools is available, demonstrating how language technologies can enhance research across various disciplines. Among these tools both desktop applications and web-based tools are included, with guidance to help users choose the right tool for their research needs. A corpus analysis tool is able to manage a corpus, display concordances, and ideally calculate frequent collocates. Many of these tools go beyond, offering features like generating word frequency lists, n-grams, clusters, linguistic annotations, and visualising word and feature distributions.

2. Normalisation

Tools for text normalisation allow the conversion of parts of a text into a single, canonical form, which is a key step in processing texts with spelling variations, such as historical documents or social media content. Once a text is normalised, it can be processed using standard tools for further linguistic analysis. One major benefit of normalisation is improved search functionality, allowing queries to be made with a standard variant while capturing all spelling variants, whether historical, dialectal, colloquial, or slang. Some tools in this category are exclusively dedicated to normalisation, while others offer additional features like PoS-tagging, lemmatisation, and named entity recognition.

3. Named Entity Recognition

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is an essential information extraction task that identifies and classifies mentions of named entities—such as people, organisations, locations, dates, and monetary values—in unstructured text. NER tools are valuable in applications like news content classification, content recommendations, search algorithms, and even sentiment analysis. Some tools focus solely on NER, while others are integrated into larger tool pipelines, offering additional features like PoS-tagging, lemmatisation, and syntactic parsing. These multifunctional tools provide a comprehensive solution for processing and analysing complex textual data across various domains.

4. Part-of-Speech Tagging and Lemmatisation

Tools for Part-of-speech (PoS) tagging automatically annotate text by assigning words or tokens to specific syntactic categories, such as nouns or verbs. These categories often include subtypes distinguished by morphosyntactic features like number or tense. Tools for lemmatisation, on the other hand, group the various inflected forms of a word under its base dictionary form. Both PoS tagging and lemmatisation are essential steps in linguistic pre-processing. An additional effort for adding morphosyntactic descriptors (MSD) may be spent when more detailed tags that account for complex inflectional systems, such as those found in Slavic languages, are needed. Many tools also offer additional functionalities, including syntactic parsing or named entity recognition.

5. Tools for Sentiment Analysis

Tools for sentiment analysis and opinion mining enhance closely related text analysis techniques used to identify and extract opinions, attitudes, and sentiments from a given text. Sentiment analysis focuses on determining the emotional tone or sentiment of a specific sentence or grammatical construction by assigning it a ternary value—such as "positive," "neutral," or "negative"—or a scalar value to indicate intensity. Opinion mining, on the other hand, targets specific parts of a text where a person's attitude, opinion, or sentiment is expressed. These methods are highly applicable in fields such as social media analysis, customer reviews, and marketing research, where understanding user opinions and feedback is crucial for gaining insights into public perception and consumer behaviour. Sentiment analysis is particularly valuable for monitoring brand sentiment, product reception, and political discourse, offering a powerful tool for understanding large-scale public opinion.

3.5 CLARIN resources described in CMDI

In order to guarantee easy access and findability to its resources, CLARIN has implemented the CMDI for the accurate, complete and interoperable descriptions of metadata. Such a solid metadata infrastructure is exploited by the VLO and FCS to harvest and gather language resources in response to queries operated by the users of the services; moreover, the semantic interoperability that results from the extensive use of CMDI supports the interchange of data and technology across and within different research domains.

In the previous paragraphs we have offered an overview of the language resources that are inside the CLARIN domain, and we have given a description of how CLARIN implements metadata descriptions thanks to CMDI and its dedicated CMDI Component Registry, which in itself is connected to the controlled vocabularies collected in the CLARIN Concept Registry.

In this paragraph, for each of the macro-categories seen in the previous paragraph (that directly derive from the CLARIN Resource Families), we give an example of CMDI description of one resource belonging to that macro-category: we will give an example of a corpus, a lexical resource and a tool for linguistic analysis, and we will concurrently analyze the correspondent CMDI profile. The three chosen resources are hosted in the ILC4CLARIN repository, the service offered by the Institute of Computational Linguistics “A. Zampolli”, National Research Council, in Pisa, as part of the Italian node of CLARIN-ERIC.

3.5.1 CMDI description of a literary corpus: Musisque Deoque (MQDQ)

Musisque Deoque, the whole corpus of the Latin poets, from the beginnings to the end of VIIIth century, was established at the end of 2005 with the main goal of creating a singular database of Latin poetry, supported by a critical and exegetical electronic apparatus. At present, main collections of classical texts have been transferred onto digital device while resources, mostly online, allow quicker lexical searches. In most cases, however, search engine inquiry only provides results of a key inside a fixed and ‘authoritarian’ text. The aim of Musisque Deoque is to overcome these limitations, allowing to locate not only the forms chosen from the text of a reference edition, but also the variants in its critical apparatus. Recent updates to the Musisque Deoque site have added key functions, including *Epigraphica*, a tool for exploring the *Carmina Latina Epigraphica* with detailed searches and a photographic archive of inscriptions. The *Witnesses* feature standardizes manuscript information, linking to libraries and digitized codices. Advanced search now includes lemma-based queries, while *Pedecerto* performs metrical scans of dactylic verse. The *Co-occurrences* feature finds rhythmic similarities across texts, and *Hellenica* offers a digital archive of Greek poetry, expanding the site’s scholarly resources.

The set of metadata associated to this resource comprises a rich description that keeps track of many aspects, like the authors and contributors that helped building this resource, the issue and availability dates, or the language(s) used in the corpus. In Appendix 1.1 we show the full item record and its corresponding metadata scheme, as seen on the web

page⁸ dedicated to the resource. By clicking on the designated link, it is possible to see the full record in XML-CMDI format: in Appendix 1.2 we show the XML-CMDI implementation of the metadata associated with MQDQ.

3.5.2 CMDI description of a lexicon: PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS

PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS is a four-level general purpose lexicon that has been elaborated over three different projects. The kernel of the morphological and syntactic lexicons was built in the framework of the European project "Preparatory Action for Linguistic Resources Organisation for Language Engineering" (LE-PAROLE). The linguistic model and the core of the semantic lexicon were elaborated within the European project "Semantic Information for Multifunctional Plurilingual Lexica" (LE-SIMPLE). The phonological level of the description and the extension of the lexical coverage were produced in the context of the Italian project "Corpora e Lessici dell'Italiano Parlato e Scritto" (CLIPS). It comprises a total of 387,267 phonetic units, 53,044 morphological units (53,044 lemmas), 37,406 syntactic units (28,111 lemmas) and 28,346 semantic units (19,216 lemmas). It was encoded at the semantic level, in full accordance with the international standards set out in the PAROLE-SIMPLE model and based on EAGLES. Syntactic and semantic encodings were performed jointly with Thamus (Consortium for Multilingual Documentary Engineering), which is responsible for 25,000 extra entries. PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS was created incrementally between the end of the 1990s and 2003.

The full item record⁹ for this resource is made as shown in Appendix 2.1. By clicking on the designated link, it is possible to see the full record in XML-CMDI format: in Appendix 2.2 we show the XML-CMDI implementation of the metadata associated with PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS.

3.5.3 CMDI description of a tool for creation of lexica in LLOD formats: DigitAnt Search

DigitAnt-search is the GUI web application of the DigitAnt platform, designed to explore, visualise and navigate the different sources of information created or linked within the national ItAnt project¹⁰. DigitAnt is an innovative platform designed to support historical linguistic and epigraphic studies, and researchers in the creation, management and consultation of digital linguistic resources for the fragmentary ancient languages. DigitAnt-search allows to explore interactively various sources of information in a unified and easily accessible environment.

The full item record¹¹ for this resource is made as shown in Appendix 3.1. By clicking on the designated link, it is possible to see the full record in XML-CMDI format: in Appendix 3.2 we show the XML-CMDI implementation of the metadata associated with DigitAnt Search tool.

⁸ The full item record and the files of the *Musisque Deoque* corpus are available at this link: <https://dspace-clarin-it.ils.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/handle/20.500.11752/OPEN-555?show=full>

⁹ The full item record and the files of PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS are available at this link: <https://dspace-clarin-it.ils.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/handle/20.500.11752/ILC-88?show=full>

¹⁰ At this link you can access the webpage of ItAnt project: <https://www.prin-italia-antica.unifi.it/>

¹¹ The full item record and the files of DigitAnt Search are available at this link: <https://dspace-clarin-it.ils.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/handle/20.500.11752/ILC-1029>

3.6 ParlaMint: a case study for semantic interoperability in CLARIN

The ParlaMint project serves as a compelling case study illustrating the importance of working within a shared semantic framework and demonstrates CLARIN's ability to manage large-scale projects while maintaining strict control over complex aspects of metadata standardization and interoperability.

The ParlaMint project¹², running from November 2019 to May 2021, aimed to build a large, comparable, and uniformly encoded corpus of European parliamentary proceedings, with an emphasis on COVID-19 discourse. The project unfolded in two phases: the first focused on developing core datasets for four countries (Croatia, Bulgaria, Poland, and Slovenia) to test workflows, followed by a call for additional partners to submit national parliamentary corpora, resulting in the addition of 13 new datasets. Later in the project, Spain joined voluntarily, bringing further diversity to the corpus. By adhering to consistent metadata standards, encoding schemes, and linguistic annotation, ParlaMint ensured that corpora from various countries were compatible with each other and with broader Parla-CLARIN standards. This alignment allowed for accurate cross-linguistic comparisons and comprehensive analysis of public discourse on the pandemic.

Each corpus followed consistent metadata standards, encoding schemes, and linguistic annotation, making them compatible with each other and the broader Parla-CLARIN standards. The corpora were divided into a COVID subcorpus (for speeches after November 2019) and a reference subcorpus (for earlier speeches). This approach enabled clear analysis of the pandemic's influence on parliamentary language across countries. The datasets include detailed metadata, distinguishing Members of Parliament (MPs), guest speakers, and procedural chairpersons, thereby enhancing the accuracy of comparative analyses.

ParlaMint's encoding framework was a collaborative, iterative effort, using bespoke RelaxNG schemas and XSLT scripts to ensure consistency and to validate corpora created by different partners. GitHub served as the main distribution platform for schemas, scripts, and corpus samples, facilitating issue tracking and collaborative development.

By the end of the project, ParlaMint had published three corpus versions. Version 1.0 provided an initial model, while Version 2.0 was near-final, released for use in a digital humanities hackathon. This feedback process led to refinements in the final Version 2.1, enhancing the data's utility for comparative studies. Each corpus is available in two variants: one with plain-text parliamentary speeches and another with advanced linguistic annotations, following Universal Dependencies formalism and including Named Entity Recognition. This approach supports broad, cross-linguistic studies on political discourse, especially in relation to public health and crisis language.

ParlaMint is considered a CLARIN flagship project: the cooperative intentions that drove the creation of the corpora resulted in the creation of a personalization of a XML schema for the encoding of the corpus, in addition to the definition of specific metadata descriptions to

¹² All the files of the ParlaMint project are available at this link: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/ParlaMint>

account for many features, such as the different roles, authority level and political orientation of speakers. These shared implementations make all ParlaMint corpora interoperable by design, because every single piece of metadata is mapped to this common semantic infrastructure of the ParlaMint project.

The full item record of the last release of ParlaMint corpus shows how much effort has been put into the detailed description of the resource: the contributors that participated in the project; the references to the XML schema and the encoding guidelines; the links to the GitHub repository where all files and scripts are hosted; the references to all the academic publications about the project itself or its exploitations; the list of all the international sponsors; the correct information about licenses and reusability recommendations.

Multilingual comparable corpora of parliamentary debates ParlaMint 4.1

“ Please use the following text to cite this item or export to a predefined format:

[BIBTEX](#) [CMDI](#)

Erjavec, Tomaž; et al., 2024, *Multilingual comparable corpora of parliamentary debates ParlaMint 4.1*, Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI, ISSN 2820-4042, <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1912>

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Figure 26: ParlaMint full item record shows all the contributors that helped in the process of creation and encoding of all the national parliamentary corpora gathered in the project.

Item identifier	http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1912	
Project URL	https://www.clarin.eu/content/parlamint	
Demo URL	https://github.com/clarin-eric/ParlaMint/	
Referenced by	https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4176128/v1	
Date issued	2024-06-03	
Type	corpus, text	
Size	8073406 utterances, 1231036093 words	
Language(s)	Basque , Bosnian , Bulgarian , Catalan , Croatian , Czech , Danish , Dutch , English , Estonian , Finnish , French , Galician , German , Hungarian , Icelandic , Italian , Latvian , Modern Greek (1453-) , Norwegian , Polish , Portuguese , Russian , Serbian , Slovenian , Spanish , Swedish , Turkish , Ukrainian	

Figure 28: A precise curation of references, repositories and demos is given in ParlaMint full item record; also, a comprehensive list of languages and subject allows optimal indexing in search queries.

Subject(s)	parliamentary debates	COVID-19	TEI	Parla-CLARIN	Czech Parliament	Icelandic Parliament	Belgian Parliament
	Danish Parliament	Dutch Parliament	Turkish Parliament	Italian Parliament	Hungarian Parliament	Latvian Parliament	
	Bulgarian Parliament	Croatian Parliament	Polish Parliament	Slovenian Parliament	French Parliament		
	Austrian Parliament	Bosnian Parliament	Catalonian Parliament	Galician Parliament	Greek Parliament		
	Norwegian Parliament	Serbian Parliament	Swedish Parliament	Ukrainian Parliament	Finnish Parliament		
	Spanish Parliament	Estonian Parliament	Basque Parliament	Portuguese Parliament	UK Parliament		

Figure 27: ParlaMint covers a plethora of subjects and topics, and each one of them is listed in the full item record.

ParlaMint's collaborative framework also highlights the effectiveness of CLARIN's infrastructure in coordinating extensive multi-partner efforts. Custom schemas and validation tools ensured consistency across datasets created by diverse contributors, while GitHub enabled centralized version control and issue tracking. This careful management allowed CLARIN to maintain high standards of interoperability, facilitating large-scale comparative research on complex, real-world issues. By exemplifying the power of a shared semantic infrastructure, ParlaMint underscores the value of CLARIN's approach to metadata control and reusability across large, multilingual datasets.

4. Modelling an ontology for Language Resources

This section delves into the current methodologies and frameworks for an ontology modelling within the domain of language resources, focusing on how the CLARIN Semantic Framework can be integrated with established ontologies like the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM) and the SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro). We begin by exploring the CIDOC CRM, a widely recognized standard for information integration in cultural heritage, which provides a common semantic framework to unify disparate data sources. Next, we examine the SSHOCro, an ontology developed to facilitate semantic interoperability across the Social Sciences and Humanities by modelling the entire data lifecycle within these disciplines.

Building on these foundations, we discuss strategies for mapping the CLARIN Semantic Framework to SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM, utilizing both top-down and bottom-up approaches. The top-down strategy involves aligning CLARIN resources at the macro level with the high-level structures of SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM. This includes categorizing CLARIN Resource Families and leveraging the CLARIN Concept Registry for controlled vocabularies to ensure interoperability. The bottom-up strategy focuses on the micro level, formalizing the granularity of tokens in language resources through a tripartite classification into DocumentToken, TextToken, and LinguisticToken. This granular approach allows for detailed representation and alignment of linguistic data across different resource types.

We illustrate these concepts through a case study involving the Musisque Deoque (MQDQ) project, demonstrating how CMDI metadata can be mapped into the proposed semantic framework to enhance semantic interoperability, then showing the correspondences between the two ways of representation.

Additionally, we propose incorporating training materials into the ontology. While training materials are not traditionally part of the CLARIN domain, this effort represents collaborative work to classify and connect these resources within the formalized ontology. Further details and refinements are ongoing, with the aim to formalize properties and descriptive metadata in subsequent developments.

By integrating CLARIN's rich language resources with broader ontological models, this section highlights the potential for enhanced data interoperability, discoverability, and reuse across the Social Sciences and Humanities, fostering more comprehensive and connected research infrastructures.

4.1 State of the art: CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro

4.1.1 CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM)

The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) is a foundational ontology for integrating cultural heritage information across museums, libraries, and archives. Developed by the ICOM/CIDOC Documentation Standards Group and designated as ISO 21127 in 2006, the CIDOC CRM provides a common semantic framework that enables interoperability by defining relationships and concepts in cultural heritage data. This “semantic glue” facilitates

consistent data mapping and sharing, allowing disparate information systems to operate within a unified global resource.

Structured to support both broad integration and specific query resolution, the CIDOC CRM includes a core set of classes and properties in CRMbase and modular extensions for specialized domains like bibliographic and geospatial data. This modularity enables cultural heritage professionals and system developers to document and link data comprehensively while preserving compatibility across disciplines.

As a formal object-oriented ontology, CIDOC CRM supports machine-readable formats (RDF, JSON-LD, XML, OWL) and uses core semantic principles: classes represent key concepts (e.g., "E21 Person"), properties define relationships (e.g., "P152 has parent"), and "properties of properties" add context (e.g., "P14.1 in the role of"). The current model includes 81 classes and 160 properties, making it both compact and adaptable. The CRM's inheritance structure ensures that subclasses share relevant properties, enabling detailed yet coherent data representation.

Designed for extensibility, CIDOC CRM allows for external additions that retain compatibility with CRMbase, ensuring effective querying and data retrieval across extensions. By supporting a shared understanding and facilitating interoperability, the CIDOC CRM has become an invaluable tool for cultural heritage information integration worldwide.

The CIDOC CRM's emphasis on semantic interoperability is essential for enabling comprehensive and nuanced analysis of cultural heritage data. By unifying information from diverse sources—such as texts, audiovisual material, and oral histories—the CRM allows scholars to reconstruct and interpret historical knowledge at scale. This framework supports both academic research and scientific evaluation by providing a consistent structure for linking and interpreting data. As a widely adopted standard, the CIDOC CRM helps bridge gaps between localized datasets and large-scale, cross-institutional repositories, empowering cultural heritage professionals to access and synthesize information from a global perspective. Its adaptability across different documentation systems makes it a versatile and effective tool for preserving and studying cultural heritage in a digitally connected world.

4.1.2 SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro)

The SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro) provides an ontological model and RDF Schema to structure and integrate data across the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC). Designed as a top-level ontology, SSHOCro establishes semantic interoperability by modelling the SSHOC data lifecycle, from collection through publication and discovery, tailored specifically to workflows in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

SSHOCro serves two main purposes: (1) standardizing metadata to trace the data lifecycle within various SSH contexts and (2) mapping and integrating existing data into interoperable information pools for future reuse. This event-based framework links data lifecycle stages

with associated research activities, supporting the documentation of data generation, publication, archiving, and access.

In practical terms, SSHOCro facilitates publishing and sharing research data in repositories, acting as “semantic glue” that converts diverse data sources into a cohesive resource for global access. It enables resource discovery and metadata summary for improved searchability. By documenting each research phase, SSHOCro creates detailed metadata records, fostering reuse and validation across projects.

Developed within the SSHOC project, SSHOCro aligns with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to meet SSH research needs, building on the CIDOC CRM. It adapts CIDOC CRM’s structure of historical events as interactions between people, objects, and ideas, extending classes and properties like *E7 Activity* and *P2 has type* to support SSH data-driven workflows. This extension provides a specialized model that bridges SSH research activities with broader frameworks for information integration.

SSHOCro’s flexible design allows it to adapt to the evolving requirements of SSH research, accommodating a wide range of data types, methods, and iterative processes typical of these fields. By providing a shared semantic foundation, SSHOCro facilitates collaboration across disciplines and institutions, supporting interdisciplinary studies that require cohesive data integration and analysis. This adaptability is especially valuable for SSH researchers who work with complex, varied datasets that demand detailed contextual metadata. Through its alignment with the CIDOC CRM and its compatibility with other ontologies, SSHOCro enables SSH researchers to maintain rigorous documentation practices while contributing to a growing, interconnected ecosystem of open science resources within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

4.2 Mapping the CLARIN Semantic Framework to the SSHOCro

The types of resources managed by CLARIN are numerous and layered, requiring a flexible approach for effective domain ontology development. For structuring the ontology, we can consider two main strategies:

1. A **top-down strategy**, where we begin with the high-level categorization of resource types at the MACRO level. Here, we focus on resource types without delving into document content at the MESO level, establishing a broad ontological framework.
2. A **bottom-up strategy**, which begins at the MICRO level with the ontologisation of tokens. This approach allows for detailed representation of internal document structure, progressively building up to the MESO level, where we examine the composition of documents.

Table 2: The three layers of CLARIN domain ontology.

Ontological Level	Description
MACRO Level	Represents high-level resource types within CLARIN, focusing on resource categorization without examining content.
MESO Level	Can be approached in two ways: (1) without exploring document content, focusing on the structure as a whole, or (2) with detailed analysis of a document's internal composition.
MICRO Level	The most granular level, focused on individual tokens within documents, allowing for precise, token-level ontologisation that supports linguistic analysis.

Both strategies have their advantages, with the top-down approach providing a structured overview of resource types across CLARIN, and the bottom-up strategy allowing for granular insights that capture the internal complexity of documents.

This section illustrates our full ontological modelling approach within Protégé, the ontology editor. Screenshots from the Protégé presentation will show the structure of the ontology, highlighting the extensions made to CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro to accommodate CLARIN-specific needs.

Our extensions focus on adapting CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro structure to better capture the nuances of language resources and analysis tools in CLARIN. For instance, we add subclasses and properties to reflect specific linguistic resource types and tool functionalities, while maintaining compatibility with CIDOC CRM's core schema.

4.2.1 Top-down strategy: integrating CLARIN with SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM

To achieve a comprehensive ontological integration of CLARIN language resources, we connect the CLARIN semantic framework with SSHOCro. This connection allows us to leverage SSHOCro's top-level ontological model and, through it, the entities and properties of CIDOC CRM. By doing so, we enable the ontologisation of CLARIN at the **MACRO level**, ensuring that language resources, tools, and workflows within the CLARIN infrastructure align with broader standards in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) domains.

SSHOCro, as a high-level ontology, provides a structure for organizing various types of resources, tools, and data lifecycle processes. It serves as a bridge to CIDOC CRM, which further expands the ontological basis to encompass concepts widely used in cultural heritage, digital humanities, and now language resource management. By mapping CLARIN resources into this combined framework, we create semantic linkages that facilitate interoperability, standardization, and reuse of language data across multiple research fields.

Figure 29: How CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro merge together; SHE1_Dataset and SHE10_Tool are our entry nodes.

The *CRM Entity* serves as the foundational or “root” node of our ontologisation, providing a flexible entry point for incorporating different types of CLARIN resources and activities. This root node allows us to organize a hierarchy that represents CLARIN Resource Families as structured subcategories.

Each resource family—such as textual resources, lexical resources, and tools—is modelled as a dedicated subclass or node. By building on this common root, we ensure that each type of resource is seamlessly integrated within a shared framework, facilitating connections between language data and other research assets.

Figure 30: CRM Entity is the root node of our ontologisation.

4.2.2 Top-down strategy: moving from the MACRO to the MESO Layer

In this ontologisation process, we begin with a high-level MACRO layer that categorizes CLARIN resources broadly within SSHOCro. As we move into more specific layers of detail, we incorporate the CLARIN Resource Families. The Resource Families are used as references to classify resources according to their type, organizing them into categories such as textual resources, linguistic resources, and tools for linguistic analysis. This classification at the MESO level allows for a structured, tiered representation of CLARIN resources that is consistent with both SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM.

Each Resource Family serves as a basis for categorization. For instance, corpora, lexical resources, and annotated texts each have distinct ontological representations, making it possible to capture the unique characteristics of different types of language data.

The CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR) plays a crucial role by providing controlled vocabularies for metadata. These vocabularies support consistent metadata creation across projects, which is essential for ensuring data compatibility and discoverability. Within the Component Metadata Infrastructure (CMDI) of CLARIN, controlled vocabularies ensure that terms and definitions are standardized, enabling researchers to accurately describe their resources. Through our ontological model, these CMDI metadata terms map to CIDOC CRM entities and properties in the form of triples, establishing clear semantic relationships. This integration aligns the metadata across both frameworks, making it easier to relate language resources to broader SSH and EOSC datasets.

4.2.3 Top-down strategy: using CLARIN Resource Families to Develop Dataset and Tool Nodes

The conceptual basis of CLARIN Resource Families enables us to structure our ontology with dedicated nodes for different Dataset and Tool types. This structured approach captures the unique qualities of each CLARIN resource category, ensuring that resources are represented accurately within CIDOC CRM. The use of Resource Families supports the creation of a clear,

Figure 31: Under SHE1_Dataset node we linked one node for each Resource Families macro-category; under SHE10_Tool we linked a node for the tools used in CLARIN infrastructure.

standardized model that can be navigated and understood across disciplines.

1. Textual Resource

The Textual Resource node includes individual documents and datasets of a primarily textual nature. Examples of textual resources in CLARIN include documents such as transcriptions, literary works, historical manuscripts, and any other textual data that can be processed linguistically.

Within our ontology, Textual Resources are represented as entities that contain structured data about the content, language, provenance, and other metadata associated with each document. For each possible type of textual resource, a specific node in the ontology has been implemented.

Figure 32: Under TextualResource node we linked a node for each type of textual resource.

2. Datasets

In this section, we break down Datasets into specific categories according to CLARIN's Resource Families.

Corpus

The Corpus subcategory includes all corpora types within the Resource Families, each representing large structured sets of language data. In the ontology, each corpus type is represented as an entity with properties detailing its structure, language, annotation type, and access rights. This approach allows for flexible mapping to CIDOC CRM properties that describe the content and structure of the corpora, enabling cross-referencing with other datasets.

Figure 33: Under the Corpus node for each type of corpus we created one corresponding node.

Lexical Resource

Under Lexical Resource, we map linguistic resources such as dictionaries, thesauri, glossaries, and other lexical datasets. These resources are crucial for linguistic analysis and are represented within the ontology with attributes that reflect their language, structure, and intended use. The use of CIDOC CRM properties here allows for interoperability with other lexical resources, both within SSH and in the broader cultural heritage domain.

Figure 34: Under the Lexical Resource node for each type of lexical resource we created one corresponding node.

3. Tool

The Tool category includes the types of tools for language analysis that are outlined in the Resource Families. These tools cover a wide array of functionalities, such as part-of-speech tagging, parsing, sentiment analysis, speech recognition, and named entity recognition. Each tool is mapped within the ontology as a type of resource used within a research process. By mapping tools in this way, we create a network of resources that link data processing activities with the datasets they generate or analyse, supporting an integrated view of the research workflow.

Figure 35: Under the Tool node for each type of tool we created one corresponding node.

4.3 Modelling Entities and Properties: Musisque Deoque (MQDQ) as a case study

To illustrate the functionality of our ontology in real-world scenarios, we applied it to the Musisque Deoque CMDI description, aligning it with SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM standards. This choice allows us to show how our ontology can integrate CLARIN CMDI metadata into a structured, interoperable format that's compatible with larger cultural heritage data networks. In the two images below, we see a direct mapping of CMDI elements—such as “Resource Type,” “Authors,” and “Funding”—into the corresponding ontology classes and properties that we modelled in our domain ontology: this binding between the two different metadata representation will be able to support semantic integration across platforms.

For instance, the CMDI’s “Resource Type” aligns with ontological classes that represent datasets in SSHOCro, supporting connections with similarly classified resources. The “Authors” field is mapped to structured entities that link researchers across databases, like ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) initiative. Moreover, elements like funding sources are contextualized with SSHOCro’s “nationalFunds” class, connecting Musisque Deoque to related projects funded under the same national initiatives.

This mapping not only enhances searchability but also enriches context by associating Musisque Deoque with standardized metadata used across the digital humanities. By bringing CIDOC CRM’s heritage-oriented model into play, our approach adds cultural significance, linking Musisque Deoque with historical research artifacts. The CMDI’s specific details are preserved while gaining a broader, ontology-driven accessibility. This example showcases how the CMDI description, paired with SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM, can serve as a bridge between detailed, project-specific metadata and a wider network of semantically integrated resources in the humanities.

Figure 36: This is the semantic tree generated by the OntoGraf plugin in Protégé, showing all the nodes and labels used to describe MQDQ.

In the second image, the ontologisation of Musisque Deoque metadata is presented using RDF triples, a fundamental structure in Semantic Web technologies that supports interoperability and linked data. RDF (Resource Description Framework) triples provide a standardised way to represent relationships between data entities in a structured, machine-readable format. Each RDF triple is composed of three parts: a subject (the entity being described), a predicate (the property or relationship), and an object (the value or related entity). For example, the CMDI metadata element for "author" is converted into a triple

where the Musisque Deoque resource is the subject, "hasAuthor" is the predicate, and the individual author entity (e.g., "AA. VV.") is the object. Similarly, the "Resource Type" and "Funding" elements from CMDI are also converted to triples that establish semantic links with related ontological classes in SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM. This process facilitates interoperability and enables the Musisque Deoque metadata to be integrated seamlessly within larger knowledge graphs.

RDF triples enable precise, semantic connections between data points, allowing diverse datasets to be linked and understood by computers in a way that preserves meaning. These triples form a graph-like structure where nodes represent entities, and edges represent relationships between them. This structure allows RDF to create a web of interconnected data, enhancing the discoverability and integration of information across different datasets and platforms.

Figure 37: Each property of MQDQ is shown as an ontological triple RDF-style.

Through these RDF triples, we ensure that metadata from Musisque Deoque can interact dynamically with other cultural heritage data resources. The conversion of CMDI metadata into ontological triples thus provides a structured, scalable approach to connecting Musisque Deoque, or any other CLARIN language resource for that matter, with related datasets in the SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM frameworks, enhancing its visibility and accessibility within digital humanities networks.

4.4 Bottom-up strategy: formalisation of the MICRO level

This section is the result of a detailed investigation into MICRO-level formalization, an area where CLARIN does not impose strict standards, apart from those necessary to ensure resource compatibility with the Language Resource Switchboard. As such, it represents original content that extends beyond the traditional scope of CLARIN, developed specifically to address the unique requirements of the infrastructures participating in H2IOSC. This work reflects a tailored approach to interoperability, designed to facilitate the integration of diverse language resources while ensuring their usability across multiple research domains. By accommodating the distinct needs of digital humanities and linguistic analysis, this

framework not only enhances the alignment of resources within H2IOSC but also supports broader research goals in open science and data-driven scholarship.

4.4.1 Granularity and Token Types in the Domain Ontology

In the domain ontology, the token is established as the minimum unit of granularity, with a tripartite classification into DocumentToken, TextToken, and LinguisticToken. This design supports interoperability and nuanced representation across three main resource types: (1) OCR and/or HTR output files in XML-ALTO or XML-PAGE formats, (2) digital scholarly editions (diplomatic, interpretative, or critical) in XML-TEI format, and (3) linguistic analysis output files, such as those in CoNLL-U format produced by tools like UDPipe. To facilitate compatibility and reuse, converters are being developed to transform these formats into RDF (XML/RDF or RDF/TTL), and alignment tools are being implemented to synchronize token streams from different types, thus ensuring integration within the Common Semantic Framework.

This tripartite token system underpins the ontology's approach to representing and classifying resource content with precision. Each of the three token types—DocumentToken, TextToken, and LinguisticToken—serves a distinct purpose, capturing different aspects of language data that are essential for various forms of analysis.

4.4.2 DocumentToken, TextToken, and LinguisticToken: Purpose and Design

1. **DocumentToken** represents the most granular digital representation of the physical segments of a document, as they appear visually or digitally in formats like XML-ALTO and XML-PAGE. DocumentTokens are structured to reflect a document's exact visual and spatial organization, addressing nuances such as line breaks, hyphenation, and layout-specific elements. This token type is crucial for preserving the physical characteristics of source texts, allowing researchers to recreate or analyse the visual layout, which can be significant in textual studies, especially for manuscripts, early printed texts, or any document with visual complexity.
2. **TextToken** functions at a level higher than DocumentToken, focusing on the continuous, logical flow of text. TextTokens represent semantically complete units within a text, capturing the continuity that may span across DocumentTokens. In cases where a word is split across lines due to hyphenation, each part would be a separate DocumentToken, but together they would form a single TextToken. This type of token is useful for preserving the cohesive flow of text within the framework of the FRBR model, which treats manifestations (physical or digital editions) as distinct representations of a work. For instance, the Latin word "*severitate*" in a manuscript split across two lines (e.g. *seve-* | *ritate*) would be represented by two DocumentTokens yet a single TextToken, preserving both the document's physical structure and the textual continuity.
3. **LinguisticToken** offers a fine-grained representation at the linguistic level, capturing elements such as morphology, syntax, and semantics. LinguisticTokens are especially useful for representing complex linguistic structures, as they allow for segmentation beyond orthographic boundaries. In the case of the Latin "*virumque*", the LinguisticToken level requires a decomposition into *virum-* and *-que*, allowing detailed linguistic analysis that acknowledges each morpheme's role. This level of

detail is critical for computational linguistic analysis and for applications requiring high granularity, such as natural language processing tasks that rely on accurate tokenization and morphosyntactic parsing.

4.4.3 Interrelationships and Many-to-Many Mapping Among Tokens

An innovative feature of this token structure is the many-to-many relationship model among DocumentTokens, TextTokens, and LinguisticTokens, which reflects the multi-layered nature of language representation.

- **DocumentToken and TextToken:** Multiple DocumentTokens can map to a single TextToken and vice versa. This relationship is particularly relevant for handling variations in document layout, such as hyphenated words split across lines. For example, as seen above, a single Latin word like *severitate* might appear across two DocumentTokens in XML-ALTO due to hyphenation, yet be represented as a single, continuous TextToken in the XML-TEI edition. This mapping preserves both the physical segmentation of the document and the uninterrupted flow of the text, offering a comprehensive representation. Additionally, in cases of *scriptio continua* found in manuscripts, a single word written continuously (e.g., *Lachiesa*, as a single DocumentToken) would be divided into multiple TextTokens in an interpretative edition to normalize textual units. This is done independently of linguistic analysis, which may further require segmentation, such as separating enclitics.
- **TextToken and LinguisticToken:** TextTokens are similarly mapped to LinguisticTokens to capture linguistic analysis that may involve segmentation within words or phrases. For instance, in Latin, *virumque* contains both the lexeme *virum-* (man) and the enclitic *-que* (and), which require separate analysis at the LinguisticToken level. This allows for detailed syntactic and semantic mapping, which would not be possible with a more generalized token system. As another example, at the textual level we may encounter place names such as *La Spezia*, *L'Aquila*, or *Il Cairo*, which appear as two separate TextTokens (e.g. *La | Spezia*). In the interpretive edition, this separation is preserved to reflect the text as it appears in written form. However, in linguistic analysis, these pairs may be combined into a single LinguisticToken to represent them as single, cohesive place names in Italian. This approach allows for a normalized linguistic interpretation while maintaining fidelity to the original text structure. This dual representation is especially beneficial for morphosyntactic and semantic parsing, as it enables accurate alignment of language data at multiple levels of analysis.

```
# text = Arma virumque cano , Troiae qui primus ab oris Italiam, fato profugus, Laviniaque venit litora, m
memorem lunonis ob iram, multa quoque et bello passus, dum conderet urbem, inferretque deos Latio,
Romae.
1   Arma   arma   ADJ sfs1n   Case=Nom|Gender=Fem|InflClass=IndEurA|Number=Sing   0
2-3 virumque _ _ _ _ _ SpacesAfter=\s\s|TokenRange=5:13
2   virum   vir   NCUN   sms2a   Case=Acc|Gender=Masc|InflClass=IndEurO|Number=Sing   1
3   que   que   CCONJ   9   1   cc   _ _
```

```
<| xml:id="d001i1" n="1">
  <w xml:id="d001w1">Arma</w>
  <w xml:id="d001w2">virumque</w>
```

Figure 38: "Virumque" is analysed as two different LinguisticTokens (picture above), but as a single TextToken (picture below)

4.4.4 Justification for the Tripartite Token Model

The proposed three-layered token model represents an innovative approach that adds value to digital humanities and computational linguistics by allowing diverse forms of tokenization within a unified framework. The distinction between DocumentToken, TextToken, and LinguisticToken enables the ontology to handle both visual and linguistic nuances, which is crucial for representing resources from disparate origins and formats (e.g., OCR/HTR files, digital scholarly editions, and linguistic analyses).

This tripartite segmentation is particularly tailored to the requirements of the CLARIN infrastructure, where linguistic analysis necessitates a high level of granularity and flexibility. The third segmentation level, LinguisticToken, is a key differentiator in CLARIN's approach, as it allows for precise handling of morphological, syntactic, and semantic elements within tokens. This structure supports advanced linguistic analysis, facilitates interoperability with other research infrastructures, and enhances the richness of language resources available for scholarly research.

In this way, the token segmentation model not only preserves the integrity of each resource type but also introduces a structured, scalable solution for integrating language data from different domains within CLARIN. Through this innovative model, the domain ontology achieves a balance between document fidelity, textual continuity, and linguistic specificity, providing a comprehensive framework for future applications in digital scholarship and language processing.

4.5 Modelling Training Materials into the ontology: a proposal

This section details the approach to formalizing Training Materials as FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) learning objects, a crucial step toward ensuring their reusability, discoverability, and interoperability within educational and research contexts. Although Training Materials are not a core focus of the CLARIN domain, they are represented in some of the infrastructure's repositories, thus they need a formal representation; moreover, their relevance to interdisciplinary knowledge makes them of essential interest within the H2IOSC framework. This work results from close collaboration with colleagues from Work Package 8 (WP8)¹³, who are focused on defining the classification and properties of these materials to ensure they meet structured learning objectives and align with H2IOSC's broader interoperability goals.

The formalization process begins by defining a structured metadata schema for Training Materials that incorporates both core descriptive elements and relational fields. These metadata fields include essential elements like title, author(s), URL, and advanced relational descriptors such as `isPartOf` and `isBasedOn`, which capture hierarchical and dependency relationships among resources. This structure allows for a dynamic representation of learning paths, courses, sections, modules, units, and individual objects, ensuring that training content can be assembled in flexible ways that support various educational

¹³ We want to thank Francesca Frontini (ILC-CNR) and Giulia Pedonese (ILC-CNR) for sharing their work and expertise on Training Materials, that are part of their contribution and effort towards Work Package 8 advancement in H2IOSC project.

contexts. By standardizing these fields, the metadata schema not only enhances the discoverability and reusability of each material but also facilitates interoperability across repositories, providing a unified approach to educational content management within H2IOSC.

In this context, we propose a preliminary classification framework, shaped significantly by the Skills4EOSC project, to align Training Materials with the ontology formalized in this deliverable. Skills4EOSC has been instrumental in defining the hierarchical structure that organizes educational content in a systematic and modular way, introducing key entities like Learning Paths, Courses, Sections, Modules, Units, and Learning Objects. The hierarchical model developed through Skills4EOSC enables a clear pedagogical flow from broad learning objectives down to specific learning items. For example, a Learning Path encompasses multiple Courses, each subdivided into Sections that contain Modules, leading down to Units and finally the most granular Learning Objects. This progression from overarching goals to specific resources allows both educators and learners to navigate the content in a structured way, facilitating targeted learning and adaptable instructional design.

Each entity within this hierarchy plays a specific role in the pedagogical framework. Learning Paths offer a roadmap to achieving comprehensive educational goals, while Courses organize content into thematic areas. Sections and Modules break down this content into more digestible, focused topics, making complex materials easier to assimilate. Units concentrate on specific competencies or topics, linked directly to Learning Objects—the datasets, documents, or tools that serve as practical resources for achieving learning outcomes. These relationships, meticulously structured and defined, ensure that educational content aligns seamlessly with the ontology’s semantic framework, facilitating semantic interoperability with other H2IOSC resources and making training content more accessible and modular across different educational settings.

Figure 39: Our proposal for an ontologisation of Training Materials, as schematised in OntoGraf.

This diagram, which was extracted from the Protégé OntoGraf representation of our ontology proposal, illustrates a hierarchical structure for organizing educational content in the form of a learning path, breaking down into various components that represent levels of granularity within the training material framework. At the top of the hierarchy, **SHE13_Work_Plan** leads to the **Learning_Path**, because a Learning Path provides an overarching roadmap for achieving broader educational objectives. A Learning Path contains **Learning_Courses**, which are further divided into **Learning_Sections**. Each section then breaks down into **Learning_Modules**, which in turn comprise **Learning_Units**. All these subdivisions are linked by the property “consists of”. Finally, at the most granular level, we have **Learning_Objects**, representing tangible resources such as datasets, documents, or tools that directly support learning outcomes. A Learning Object is connected to a Learning Unit by the property “used specific object”.

Figure 40: Learning Path, Course, Sections, Modules and Units are hierarchical subclasses linked by the property "consists of" (picture above), whereas a Learning Unit connects to a Learning Object with the property "used specific object" (picture below).

In addition to this hierarchy, the previous diagram shows links to other entities like the CIDOC CRM **Activity** and the SSHOCro **SHE4_Service**, indicating that these learning elements are interconnected with various services and activities that support the educational process. For instance, **SHE4_Service** connects to multiple levels, from Learning Modules down to Learning Objects, suggesting that specific services or resources reflect the nature of multiple stages of the learning journey. There is also a **SHE1_Dataset** connected to **Learning_Objects**, showing that the Learning Object themselves consist of materials (which could be text, video, audio, images, presentations or interacted media) provided to learners, reinforcing the applied, resource-driven approach in these educational structures.

The Skills4EOSC project, closely connected to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), not only supported the creation of this classification framework but also promotes FAIR-by-design methodologies tailored to the needs of training and skills development within EOSC. By establishing standards and best practices for FAIR training resources, Skills4EOSC ensures

that these materials remain high-quality, discoverable, and reusable, ultimately helping diverse stakeholders gain the competencies needed for engagement with EOSC. Skills4EOSC's commitment to FAIR principles directly supports EOSC's mission to create a unified, interoperable training catalogue, which will streamline access to resources and foster sustainable knowledge sharing and skill development across the open science community.

At the heart of this deliverable is the construction of an ontology for language resources. This ontology is designed to model the relationships among language resources, tools, and scholarly concepts, providing a structured framework that enables consistent representation and integration of diverse data sets. Drawing from established models such as the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) and the SSHOCro ontology, the ontology proposed in this deliverable aims to standardize how language resources are described and interconnected across multiple platforms and disciplines. By formalizing these relationships in a semantic structure, the ontology will enhance both machine and human interpretability of language resources, fostering seamless data discovery, sharing, and usage. This foundational work is key to achieving the broader goals of H2IOSC, as it not only ensures that language resources can be accessed and used within the context of the CLARIN infrastructure but also contributes to the development of a Common Semantic Framework that will integrate language resources with other domains within the humanities and cultural heritage sectors.

This classification framework for Training Materials will be refined and enriched over time, while WP8 continues to refine both the structure and associated metadata descriptors, capturing pedagogical and technical nuances that ensure each component of the model is both comprehensive and adaptable. As this framework evolves, it will formalize descriptive properties and metadata schemas that connect Training Materials seamlessly with other H2IOSC resources, creating a cohesive and interoperable system that advances both educational and research objectives within the H2IOSC ecosystem. This ongoing development reflects a shared commitment to building an infrastructure that supports open science and lifelong learning in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

5. Conclusions

The "Workflow to Ensure Interoperability for Language Resources and Tools" deliverable has established a solid foundation for fostering interoperability of language resources and tools within the H2IOSC ecosystem. By integrating metadata standards, developing ontological frameworks, and creating practical workflows, this effort has taken significant strides toward achieving semantic alignment across multiple research infrastructures. These accomplishments lay the groundwork for future advancements in the integration, accessibility, and usability of language resources and tools.

5.1 Key Achievements

This deliverable has achieved critical milestones that strengthen the interoperability framework within H2IOSC:

- **Adoption of Metadata Standards:** By showcasing the CLARIN Semantic Framework, which describes linguistic resources through CMDI and CCR, this deliverable demonstrates how these elements align metadata with FAIR principles to ensure consistency, findability, and reusability. Moreover, this framework can serve as a valuable reference point for establishing a clear roadmap for the future work of WP4, guiding efforts to expand and refine the semantic infrastructure needed to support H2IOSC's broader objectives.
- **Integration of Core Tools:** The tools developed and implemented by CLARIN, such as the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), Federated Content Search (FCS), and Language Resource Switchboard (LRS), serve as valuable examples that can strengthen and enhance the infrastructure envisioned by H2IOSC. These tools demonstrate how resource discovery and accessibility can be effectively optimized, providing a model that H2IOSC can adapt and expand to meet its broader interoperability and integration goals.
- **Development of an Ontological Framework:** Progress in creating an ontology based on the CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro models has enabled the representation of complex relationships among resources, tools, and scholarly concepts, supporting semantic interoperability across H2IOSC. This ontology not only provides a structured framework for organizing linguistic and cultural heritage resources but also establishes a bridge between domain-specific metadata systems and a broader, cross-disciplinary semantic infrastructure. By aligning CLARIN's CMDI and CCR frameworks with CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro, the ontology facilitates deeper integration and more meaningful connections between diverse datasets, paving the way for the development of H2IOSCro. This expanded framework, a key outcome of WP4's efforts, will enhance H2IOSC's ability to represent, share, and analyse resources in a unified, interoperable environment.

5.2 Future Actions and Strategic Priorities

Looking ahead, the success of this deliverable provides a roadmap for several critical actions to enhance interoperability and maximize the impact of H2IOSC's infrastructure:

- **Collaboration with WP5:** Ensuring close and continuous interaction between WP4 and WP5 is essential. WP5's ontological framework complements the advancements made in this deliverable and will be instrumental in aligning resources across H2IOSC for exposing them in the future marketplace. Regular communication between the work packages will help harmonize overlapping domains, address inconsistencies, and ensure that any areas currently underspecified are comprehensively modelled to meet both educational and research requirements.
- **Inter-Infrastructure Integration:** Collaboration within and beyond H2IOSC is vital for ensuring compatibility with other European research infrastructures. Establishing clear intersections with these infrastructures will identify overlapping areas where alignment is needed. Some overlaps may converge naturally, while others might require harmonization through negotiation. In certain cases, extensions may be necessary to address underspecified areas. This integration will promote a unified ecosystem where language resources are interoperable across various domains, fostering broader collaboration and innovation.
- **Prioritization of Domain-Specific Resources:** While general interoperability has been a primary focus, domain-specific resources unique to CLARIN must now be prioritized. Pre-ontologized linguistic resources, which are easily adaptable to the H2IOSC ontology, should take precedence to demonstrate quick wins. Simultaneously, attention should be given to more complex resources that require further ontologisation. Strategic discussions within the infrastructure will help identify key resources that can be targeted for ontologisation, in order to establish H2IOSC's expertise in language resource interoperability.
- **Development of Conversion Tools:** Streamlining data integration will depend heavily on the creation and refinement of conversion tools. These tools must support the transformation of CMDI metadata into RDF triples and the conversion of raw data into semantically enriched ontological representations. Such capabilities will ensure that resources within H2IOSC are not only compatible with the ontology but also contribute to a cohesive and machine-readable semantic framework. This action is critical to maintaining the momentum of interoperability advancements and enabling seamless data sharing across platforms.

5.3 Proposed Methodology for Cross-Domain Discussion

To address the challenges of cross-domain interoperability and ensure effective resolution of overlapping elements, the following methodology is proposed:

- **Structured Dialogue Framework:** Establishing a systematic and transparent process for cross-domain discussions is essential. This framework should prioritize areas that

require harmonization, such as domains where similar concepts are expressed differently, and identify where extensions or revisions are necessary. Clear guidelines for evaluating and addressing overlapping elements will help streamline the negotiation process and prevent duplication of effort.

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving key experts and stakeholders, including other WPs representatives, domain-specific leaders, and external infrastructure partners, will be crucial. Their input will ensure that diverse perspectives are considered, and practical solutions are developed. Regular workshops, consultations, and collaborative sessions should be organized to address critical challenges and facilitate knowledge sharing.
- **Roadmap for Ontological Alignment:** A well-defined timeline with clear milestones is essential to ensure steady progress toward alignment. This roadmap should outline short-term goals, such as addressing specific overlapping elements, and long-term objectives, like fully integrating ontologies within H2IOSC. Regular assessments should be conducted to evaluate progress and refine the roadmap as needed, ensuring it remains aligned with H2IOSC's broader objectives.
- **Prioritization of Overlapping Areas:** For overlapping elements, it is crucial to classify them into categories: those that naturally converge and require minimal discussion, those needing harmonization due to differing representations, and those requiring extensions to fill gaps. This classification will help focus efforts on areas with the highest impact potential and avoid unnecessary delays in simpler cases.
- **Mechanisms for Harmonization and Extension:** For areas requiring harmonization, standardized templates and negotiation protocols should be established to ensure consistency across domains. In cases where extensions are needed, collaborative teams can work on specifying these additions while maintaining compatibility with existing models. Critical apparatuses and other underspecified elements should be evaluated for their potential integration into the ontology.

By implementing this methodology, H2IOSC can foster productive dialogue, resolve challenges efficiently, and ensure that its ontology becomes a robust and interoperable framework not only within the project but also across the broader European research ecosystem.

5.4 Closing Remarks

The advancements presented in this deliverable reinforce H2IOSC's commitment to advancing interoperability as a cornerstone of open science. By continuing to develop a unified framework for language resources and tools, H2IOSC will strengthen its position as a leader in the digital transformation of the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. These efforts not only support collaboration and innovation within H2IOSC but also contribute to the broader goals of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). By setting a benchmark for the integration and use of digital resources in research infrastructures, H2IOSC is fostering

an inclusive and forward-looking ecosystem that supports research and education across diverse domains.

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Erjavec, T., Ogrodniczuk, M., Osenova, P., Ljubešić, N., Simov, K., Pančur, A., Rudolf, M., Kopp, M., Barkarson, S., Steingrímsson, S., Çöltekin, Ç., De Does, J., Depuydt, K., Agnoloni, T., Venturi, G., Pérez, M. C., De Macedo, L. D., Navarretta, C., Luxardo, G., ... Fišer, D. (2023). The ParlaMint corpora of parliamentary proceedings. *Language Resources and Evaluation*, 57(1), 415–448. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10579-021-09574-0>

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Appendix

1.1 MQDQ full item record

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dc.language.iso	grc
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dc.publisher	Venice Centre for Digital and Public Humanities (VePDH)
dc.publisher	Università Ca' Foscari Venezia
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dc.rights	Creative Commons - Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0)
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demo.uri	https://www.mqdq.it/public/ricerca/avanzata
contact.person	Paolo Mastandrea mast@unive.it Università Ca' Foscari Venezia
sponsor	MIUR PRIN 2005; PRIN 2007 Musisque Deoque nationalFunds
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1.2 MQDQ XML-CMDI

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database of Latin poetry, supported by a critical and exegetical electronic apparatus. At present,
main collections of classical texts have been transferred onto digital device while resources, mostly
online, allow quicker lexical searches. In most cases, however, search engine inquiry only provides
results of a key inside a fix and 'authoritarian' text. The aim of Musisque Deoque is to overcome
these limitations, allowing to locate not only the forms chosen from the text of a reference edition,
but also the variants in its critical apparatus. Lately, the website has been implemented with new
functions. These are the most important: Epigraphica, i. e. a peculiar handling of the Carmina Latina
Epigraphica, with a search by corpora, by incipit, other information about place of origin, dating,
when existing a paratext in prose, etc.; in addition, a photographic archive of the inscriptions on
catalogue has been set up. Witnesses: the site has been supplied, in the apparatuses, with a standard
nomenclature of the manuscripts, displaying the current proper names of city, library, collection and
the signature; a list of poets and works that are present in the same manuscript; a link to the
library's website and, if existing, to the digitized images of the codex. Search by lemmas: available
in the advanced search; Metrical scan of all the works in dactylic verses, performed by the Pedecerto
application. Co-occurrences: starting from a chosen source text, the whole corpus is investigated to
find verbal or non-verbal rhythmic similarities. Hellenica: a digital archive of Greek
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2.1 PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS full item record

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dc.date.accessioned	2017-12-06T11:40:22Z
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dc.identifier.uri	http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-88
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dc.language.iso	ita
dc.publisher	Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "A. Zampolli" - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (ILC-CNR)
dc.rights	Creative Commons - Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0)
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dc.subject	Morfologia
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metashare.ResourceInfo#ContentInfo .mediaType	text
has.files	yes
branding	ILC
contact.person	Monica Monachini risorse@ilc.cnr.it CNR-ILC
sponsor	Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca CLIPS Corpora e Lessici dell'Italiano Parlato e Scritto nationalFunds

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2.2 PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS XML-CMDI

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    <cmd:MdSelfLink>https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-88@format=cmdi</cmd:MdSelfLink>
    <cmd:MdProfile>clarin.eu:cr1:p_1403526079380</cmd:MdProfile>
    <cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName>ILC4CLARIN : ILC Data & Tools</cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName>
  </cmd:Header>
  <cmd:Resources>
```

```

<cmd:ResourceProxyList>
  <cmd:ResourceProxy id="lp_49">
    <cmd:ResourceType>LandingPage</cmd:ResourceType>
    <cmd:ResourceRef>https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-88</cmd:ResourceRef>
  </cmd:ResourceProxy>
  <cmd:ResourceProxy id="uri_1">
    <cmd:ResourceType mimetype="text/html">Resource</cmd:ResourceType>
    <cmd:ResourceRef>http://www.ilc.cnr.it/en/content/clips</cmd:ResourceRef>
  </cmd:ResourceProxy>
  <cmd:ResourceProxy id="_166">
    <cmd:ResourceType mimetype="application/gzip">Resource</cmd:ResourceType>
    <cmd:ResourceRef lindat:md5_checksum="da32569591aed44e5e52411d2d83a5c3">https://dspace-clarin-
it.ilc.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/bitstream/handle/20.500.11752/ILC-
88/simplelexicon.sql.tar.gz?sequence=1</cmd:ResourceRef>
  </cmd:ResourceProxy>
</cmd:ResourceProxyList>
<cmd:JournalFileProxyList/>
<cmd:ResourceRelationList/>
</cmd:Resources>
<cmd:Components>
  <cmd:LINDAT_CLARIN>
    <cmd:bibliographicInfo>
      <cmd:projectUrl>http://www.ilc.cnr.it/en/content/clips</cmd:projectUrl>
      <cmd:titles>
        <cmd:title xml:lang="en">PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS</cmd:title>
      </cmd:titles>
      <cmd:authors>
        <author xmlns="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/">
          <lastName>AA. VV.</lastName>
        </author>
      </cmd:authors>
      <cmd:dates>
        <cmd:dateIssued>2016-11-21</cmd:dateIssued>
      </cmd:dates>
      <cmd:identifiers>
        <cmd:identifier type="Handle">https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-88</cmd:identifier>
      </cmd:identifiers>
      <cmd:funds>
        <funding xmlns="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/">
          <organization>Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca</organization>
          <code>CLIPS</code>
          <projectName>Corpora e Lessici dell'Italiano Parlato e Scritto</projectName>
          <fundsType>nationalFunds</fundsType>
        </funding>
      </cmd:funds>
      <contactPerson xmlns="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/">
        <firstName>Monica</firstName>
        <lastName>Monachini</lastName>
        <email>risorse@ilc.cnr.it</email>
        <affiliation>CNR-ILC</affiliation>
      </contactPerson>
      <cmd:publishers>
        <cmd:publisher>Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "A. Zampolli" - Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche (ILC-CNR)</cmd:publisher>
      </cmd:publishers>
    </cmd:bibliographicInfo>
    <cmd:dataInfo>
      <cmd:type>lexicalConceptualResource</cmd:type>
      <cmd:detailedType>computationalLexicon</cmd:detailedType>
      <cmd:description>PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS is a four-level general purpose lexicon that has been
elaborated over three different projects. The kernel of the morphological and syntactic lexicons was
built in the framework of the European project "Preparatory Action for Linguistic Resources
Organisation for Language Engineering" (LE-PAROLE). The linguistic model and the core of the semantic
lexicon were elaborated within the European project "Semantic Information for Multifunctional
Plurilingual Lexica" (LE-SIMPLE). The phonological level of the description and the extension of the
lexical coverage were produced in the context of the Italian project "Corpora e Lessici dell'Italiano
Parlato e Scritto" (CLIPS). It comprises a total of 387,267 phonetic units, 53,044 morphological units
(53,044 lemmas), 37,406 syntactic units (28,111 lemmas) and 28,346 semantic units (19,216 lemmas). It
was encoded at the semantic level, in full accordance with the international standards set out in the
PAROLE-SIMPLE model and based on EAGLES. Syntactic and semantic encodings were performed jointly with
Thamus (Consortium for Multilingual Documentary Engineering), which is responsible for 25,000 extra

```

entries. PAROLE-SIMPLE-CLIPS was created incrementally between the end of the 1990s and 2003.</cmd:description>

```
<cmd:languages>
  <cmd:language>
    <cmd:code>ita</cmd:code>
    <cmd:name>Italian</cmd:name>
  </cmd:language>
</cmd:languages>
<cmd:keywords>
  <cmd:keyword>Database lessicale</cmd:keyword>
  <cmd:keyword>Morfologia</cmd:keyword>
  <cmd:keyword>Semantica lessicale</cmd:keyword>
  <cmd:keyword>Fonologia</cmd:keyword>
  <cmd:keyword>Lessico computazionale</cmd:keyword>
  <cmd:keyword>Sintassi</cmd:keyword>
  <cmd:keyword>Lexical database</cmd:keyword>
  <cmd:keyword>Morphology</cmd:keyword>
</cmd:keywords>
<cmd:sizeInfo>
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    <size>37.406</size>
    <unit>syntacticUnits</unit>
  </size>
  <size xmlns="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/">
    <size>28.346</size>
    <unit>semanticUnits</unit>
  </size>
  <size xmlns="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/">
    <size>387,267</size>
    <unit>phoneticUnits</unit>
  </size>
  <size xmlns="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/">
    <size>53,044</size>
    <unit>morphologicalUnits</unit>
  </size>
</cmd:sizeInfo>
</cmd:dataInfo>
<cmd:licenseInfo>
  <cmd:license>
    <cmd:uri>http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/</cmd:uri>
  </cmd:license>
</cmd:licenseInfo>
</cmd:LINDAT_CLARIN>
</cmd:Components>
</cmd:CMD>
```

3.1 DigItAnt Search full item record

dc.contributor.author	Mallia, Michele
dc.contributor.author	Quochi, Valeria
dc.date.accessioned	2024-10-16T07:02:15Z
dc.date.available	2024-10-16T07:02:15Z
dc.date.issued	2024-09-19
dc.identifier.uri	http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-1029
dc.description	<p>DigItAnt-search is the GUI web application of the DigItAnt platform, designed to explore, visualise and navigate the different sources of information created or linked within the national ItAnt project (https://www.prin-italia-antica.unifi.it/). DigItAnt is an innovative platform designed to support historical linguistic and epigraphic studies, and researchers in the creation, management and consultation of digital linguistic resources for the fragmentary ancient languages. DigItAnt-search allows to explore interactively various sources of information in a unified and easily accessible environment. The development of DigItAnt was funded by the Ministry of University and Research under the program Research Projects of Relevant National Interest (PRIN) 2017. This front-end application was developed by Michele Mallia under the supervision of Valeria Quochi and thanks to continuous discussion and exchange with the team, composed of: Andrea Bellandi, Alessandro Tommasi, Cesare Zavattari, Silvia Piccini, Michela Bandini, Chiara Fazzone.</p>
dc.publisher	Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "A. Zampolli" - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (ILC-CNR)
dc.source.uri	https://github.com/DigItAnt/DigItAnt_search
dc.subject	Historical Linguistics
dc.subject	Digital Epigraphy
dc.subject	Linguistic Linked Data
dc.subject	Web GUI Application
dc.subject	Search Interface
dc.title	DigItAnt Search

dc.type	toolService
metashare.ResourceInfo#ContentInfo.detailedType	other
metashare.ResourceInfo#ResourceComponentType#ToolServiceInfo.languageDependent	false
has.files	no
branding	ILC
demo.uri	https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/platform/
contact.person	Michele Mallia michele.mallia@ilc.cnr.it michele.mallia@ilc.cnr.it
contact.person	Valeria Quochi valeria.quochi@ilc.cnr.it valeria.quochi@ilc.cnr.it
sponsor	MUR PRIN 2017XJLE8Jf Languages and Cultures of Ancient Italy. Historical Linguistics and Digital Models (ItAnt) nationalFunds
files.size	0
files.count	0

3.2 DigItAnt Search XML-CMDI

```
<cmd:CMD xmlns:cmd="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/"
xmlns:lindat="http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/ns/experimental/cmdi" xmlns:olac="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/"
xmlns:ms="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
CMDVersion="1.1" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.clarin.eu/cmd/
http://catalog.clarin.eu/ds/ComponentRegistry/rest/registry/profiles/clarin.eu:cr1:p_1349361150622/xsd
">
  <cmd:Header>
    <cmd:MdCreationDate>2024-10-16</cmd:MdCreationDate>
    <cmd:MdSelfLink>https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-1029@format=cmdi</cmd:MdSelfLink>
    <cmd:MdProfile>clarin.eu:cr1:p_1349361150622</cmd:MdProfile>
    <cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName>ILC4CLARIN : ILC Data & Tools</cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName>
  </cmd:Header>
  <cmd:Resources>
    <cmd:ResourceProxyList>
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      </cmd:ResourceProxy>
      <cmd:ResourceProxy id="uri_1">
        <cmd:ResourceType mimetype="text/html">Resource</cmd:ResourceType>
        <cmd:ResourceRef>https://github.com/DigItAnt/DigItAnt_search</cmd:ResourceRef>
      </cmd:ResourceProxy>
    </cmd:ResourceProxyList>
    <cmd:JournalFileProxyList/>
    <cmd:ResourceRelationList/>
  </cmd:Resources>
  <cmd:Components>
    <cmd:data>
      <olac:OLAC-DcmiTerms>
        <olac:available>2024-10-16T07:02:15Z</olac:available>
        <olac:creator>Mallia, Michele</olac:creator>
        <olac:creator>Quochi, Valeria</olac:creator>
        <olac:date>2024-10-16T07:02:15Z</olac:date>
        <olac:description>DigItAnt-search is the GUI web application of the DigItAnt platform,
designed to explore, visualise and navigate the different sources of information created or linked
within the national ItAnt project (https://www.prin-italia-antica.unifi.it/). DigItAnt is an
innovative platform designed to support historical linguistic and epigraphic studies, and researchers
in the creation, management and consultation of digital linguistic resources for the fragmentary
ancient languages. DigItAnt-search allows to explore interactively various sources of information in a
unified and easily accessible environment. The development of DigItAnt was funded by the Ministry of
University and Research under the program Research Projects of Relevant National Interest (PRIN) 2017.
This front-end application was developed by Michele Mallia under the supervision of Valeria Quochi and
```

```
thanks to continuous discussion and exchange with the team, composed of: Andrea Bellandi, Alessandro Tommasi, Cesare Zavattari, Silvia Piccini, Michela Bandini, Chiara Fazzino.</olac:description>  
<olac:identifier>http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/ILC-1029</olac:identifier>  
<olac:issued>2024-09-19</olac:issued>  
<olac:publisher>Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "A. Zampolli" - Consiglio Nazionale  
delle Ricerche (ILC-CNR)</olac:publisher>  
<olac:source>https://github.com/DigItAnt/DigItAnt_search</olac:source>  
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<olac:subject>Digital Epigraphy</olac:subject>  
<olac:subject>Linguistic Linked Data</olac:subject>  
<olac:subject>Web GUI Application</olac:subject>  
<olac:subject>Search Interface</olac:subject>  
<olac:title>DigItAnt Search</olac:title>  
<olac:type>toolService</olac:type>  
</olac:OLAC-DcmlTerms>  
</cmd:data>  
</cmd:Components>  
</cmd:CMD>
```

Annex

1. CLARIN ontology in ttl format

```
@prefix : <http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/> .
@prefix ceo: <http://purl.org/critical-edition-ontology/> .
# source: https://github.com/ChiaraMartignano/critical-edition-ontology/tree/main/docs
@prefix crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/> .
# source: https://cidoc-crm.org/html/cidoc_crm_v7.1.3.html
@prefix geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#> .
# Source: https://opengeospatial.github.io/ogc-geosparql/geosparql11/geo.ttl
@prefix lrm: <http://iflastandards.info/ns/lrm/lrmoo/> .
# source: https://gitlab.isl.ics.forth.gr/cidoc-crm/compatible-models/lrmoo/-/tree/main/1.0
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix xml: <http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix sshoc: <http://www.ics.forth.gr/SSHOC/> .
# source: documented at: https://zenodo.org/records/3744861
@prefix crmtex: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/extensions/crmtex#> .
# source: https://gitlab.isl.ics.forth.gr/cidoc-crm/compatible-models/crmtex/-
/tree/v2.0_preparation/2.0
@prefix ontolex: <http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/ontolex#> .
# source: http://www.w3.org/ns/lemon/ontolex
@base <http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/> .

#####
# Annotation properties
#####

### http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P107_has_current_or_former_affiliation
crm:P107_has_current_or_former_affiliation rdf:type owl:AnnotationProperty .

### http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P131_is_identified_by
crm:P131_is_identified_by rdf:type owl:AnnotationProperty .

### http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P3_has_note
crm:P3_has_note rdf:type owl:AnnotationProperty .

### http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P91_has_unit
crm:P91_has_unit rdf:type owl:AnnotationProperty .

#####
# Datatypes
#####

### http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#date
xsd:date rdf:type rdfs:Datatype .

#####
# Object Properties
#####

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/first_cts_urn
:first_cts_urn rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :TextPassage ;
  rdfs:range :CTSURN .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_baseline
:has_baseline rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :Line ;
  rdfs:range :Baseline ;
  rdfs:comment "Relates a Line to its Baseline." ;
  rdfs:label "has baseline" .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_cts_urn
:has_cts_urn rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:domain [ rdf:type owl:Class ;
                    owl:unionOf ( :DocumentObject
                                   :TextObject
                                )
                  ] ;
      rdfs:range :CTSURN .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_division_type
:has_division_type rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:subPropertyOf crm:P2_has_type ;
      rdfs:domain :Division ;
      rdfs:range :DivisionType ;
      rdfs:comment "Relates a Division to its DivisionType." ;
      rdfs:label "has division type" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_document_position
:has_document_position rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:domain :DocumentObject .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_line_type
:has_line_type rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:subPropertyOf crm:P2_has_type ;
      rdfs:domain :Line ;
      rdfs:range :LineType ;
      rdfs:comment "Relates a Line to its LineType." ;
      rdfs:label "has line type" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_polygon
:has_polygon rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:domain :Shape ;
      rdfs:range :Polygon ;
      rdfs:comment "Relates a Shape to its Polygon." ;
      rdfs:label "has polygon" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_segment_type
:has_segment_type rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:subPropertyOf crm:P2_has_type ;
      rdfs:domain :Segment ;
      rdfs:range :SegmentType ;
      rdfs:comment "Relates a Segment to its SegmentType." ;
      rdfs:label "has segment type" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_shape
:has_shape rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:domain crm:E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing ;
      rdfs:range :Shape ;
      rdfs:comment "Relates a Thing to its Shape." ;
      rdfs:label "has shape" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_text_passages
:has_text_passages rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
      rdfs:domain :Citation ;
      rdfs:range [ owl:intersectionOf ( rdf:List
                                         [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
                                           owl:onProperty rdf:first ;
                                           owl:allValuesFrom :TextPassage
                                         ]
                                         [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
                                           owl:onProperty rdf:rest ;
                                           owl:allValuesFrom [ rdf:type owl:Class ;
                                                                    owl:unionOf ( rdf:List
```

```
owl:Nothing
)
]
) ;
rdf:type owl:Class
] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/copih/has_text_position
:has_text_position rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :TextObject .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/copih/has_token_part
:has_token_part rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :Token ;
  rdfs:range :Token ;
  rdfs:comment "Relates a Token to its Token part." ;
  rdfs:label "has token part" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/copih/has_token_type
:has_token_type rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :Token ;
  rdfs:range :TokenType ;
  rdfs:comment "Relates a Token to its TokenType." ;
  rdfs:label "has token type" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/copih/has_written_space_type
:has_written_space_type rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:subPropertyOf crm:P2_has_type ;
  rdfs:domain :WrittenSpace ;
  rdfs:range :WrittenSpaceType ;
  rdfs:comment "Relates a WrittenSpace to its WrittenSpaceType." ;
  rdfs:label "has written space type" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/copih/has_zone_type
:has_zone_type rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:subPropertyOf crm:P2_has_type ;
  rdfs:domain :Zone ;
  rdfs:range :ZoneType ;
  rdfs:comment "Relates a Zone to its ZoneType." ;
  rdfs:label "has zone type" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/copih/last_cts_urn
:last_cts_urn rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :TextPassage ;
  rdfs:range :CTSURN .

### http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#as_linestring
geo:as_linestring rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :Baseline ;
  rdfs:range geo:wktLiteral .

### http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#as_polygon
geo:as_polygon rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty ;
  rdfs:domain :Polygon ;
  rdfs:range geo:wktLiteral .

### http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#first
rdf:first rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty .

### http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#rest
rdf:rest rdf:type owl:ObjectProperty .
```

```
#####
#   Data properties
#####

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_document_position
:has_document_position rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
                        rdfs:range rdfs:Literal .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/has_text_position
:has_text_position rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
                    rdfs:range rdfs:Literal .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/height
:height rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
         rdfs:domain crm:E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing ;
         rdfs:range xsd:integer .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/hpos
:hpos rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
       rdfs:domain crm:E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing ;
       rdfs:range xsd:integer .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/vpos
:vpos rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
       rdfs:domain crm:E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing ;
       rdfs:range xsd:integer .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/width
:width rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty ;
        rdfs:domain crm:E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing ;
        rdfs:range xsd:integer .

### http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#as_linestring
:as_linestring rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty .

### http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#as_polygon
:as_polygon rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty .

### http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#value
:value rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty .

#####
#   Classes
#####

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/AcademicTextCorpus
:AcademicTextCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
                    rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
                    rdfs:label "Corpus of Academic Texts"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Actor_Appellation
:Actor_Appellation rdf:type owl:Class ;
                   rdfs:subClassOf crm:E41_Appellation .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Baseline
:Baseline rdf:type owl:Class ;
           rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ;
           rdfs:comment "The baseline of a text line" ;
           rdfs:label "Baseline" .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/CTSURN
:CTSURN rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E90_Symbolic_Object .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/CharacterSequence
:CharacterSequence rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E90_Symbolic_Object ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty rdf:value ;
    owl:allValuesFrom rdfs:Literal
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Citation
:Citation rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E90_Symbolic_Object .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Codex
:Codex rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :DiplomaticEdition ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P46_is_composed_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Layout
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/CodexFacsimile
:CodexFacsimile rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Facsimile ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P46_is_composed_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :LayoutFacsimile
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ComputerMediatedCommunicationCorpus
:ComputerMediatedCommunicationCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Computer-Mediated Communication Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ConceptualResource
:ConceptualResource rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :LexicalResource ;
  rdfs:label "Conceptual Resource"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Contact_Point
:Contact_Point rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E41_Appellation .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Corpus
:Corpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE1_Dataset ;
  rdfs:comment "A collection of structured language data, such as text or speech, that is used
for linguistic research."@en ;
  rdfs:label "Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/CorpusQueryTool
:CorpusQueryTool rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Tool ;
  rdfs:label "Corpus Query Tool"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/CriticalEdition
:CriticalEdition rdf:type owl:Class ;
```

```
        rdfs:subClassOf :ScholarlyEdition ,
                    ceo:CriticalEdition .

:LiteraryCriticalEdition rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :LiteraryTextResource ,
        :CriticalEdition .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Dictionary
:Dictionary rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :LexicalResource ;
    rdfs:label "Dictionary"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Digital_Human-Made_Feature
:Digital_Human-Made_Feature rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Thing .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Digital_Human-Made_Thing
:Digital_Human-Made_Thing rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E71_Human-Made_Thing .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DiplomaticEdition
:DiplomaticEdition rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DocumentResource ,
        :ScholarlyEdition .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DisorderedSpeechCorpus
:DisorderedSpeechCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
    rdfs:label "Corpus of Disordered Speech"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Division
:Division rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E90_Symbolic_Object ,
        [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
          owl:onProperty :has_division_type ;
          owl:allValuesFrom :DivisionType
        ] ,
        [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
          owl:onProperty crm:P46_is_composed_of ;
          owl:allValuesFrom [ rdf:type owl:Class ;
                                owl:unionOf ( :Division
                                                :Token
                                                )
                              ]
        ]
    ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DivisionType
:DivisionType rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E55_Type .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DocumentDivision
:DocumentDivision rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Division ,
        :DocumentObject .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DocumentDivisionType
:DocumentDivisionType rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DocumentObject
:DocumentObject rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E73_Information_Object .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DocumentResource
:DocumentResource rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE1_Dataset .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DocumentToken
:DocumentToken rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DocumentObject ,
        :Token .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/FacsimilarEdition
:FacsimilarEdition rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DocumentResource ,
        :ScholarlyEdition .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Facsimile
:Facsimile rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :TextResource .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Glossary
:Glossary rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :LexicalResource ;
    rdfs:label "Glossary"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Glyph
:Glyph rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/HTRDocument
:HTRDocument rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :TextRecognitionDocument .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/HistoricalCorpus
:HistoricalCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
    rdfs:label "Historical Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/InterpretiveEdition
:InterpretiveEdition rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DocumentResource ,
        :ScholarlyEdition .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LanguageModel
:LanguageModel rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :LexicalResource ;
    rdfs:label "Language Model"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Layout
:Layout rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :DiplomaticEdition ,
        [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
            owl:onProperty crm:P56_bears_feature ;
            owl:allValuesFrom :Page
        ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LayoutFacsimile
:LayoutFacsimile rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Facsimile .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LearnerCorpus
:LearnerCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "L2 Learner Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Learning_Course
:Learning_Course rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE4_Service ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P9_consists_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Learning_Section
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Learning_Module
:Learning_Module rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE4_Service ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P9_consists_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Learning_Unit
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Learning_Object
:Learning_Object rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE1_Dataset .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Learning_Path
:Learning_Path rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE13_Work_Plan ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P9_consists_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Learning_Course
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Learning_Section
:Learning_Section rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE4_Service ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P9_consists_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Learning_Module
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Learning_Unit
:Learning_Unit rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE4_Service ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P16_used_specific_object ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Learning_Object
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LegalCorpus
:LegalCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Legal Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Legal_Body
:Legal_Body rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E72_Legal_Object .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LexicalResource
:LexicalResource rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE1_Dataset ;
  rdfs:label "Lexical Resource"@en .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Lexicon
:Lexicon rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :LexicalResource ;
  rdfs:label "Lexicon"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Line
:Line rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P56_bears_feature ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Segment
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LineType
:LineType rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E55_Type .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LinguisticDivision
:LinguisticDivision rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Division ,
  crm:E33_Linguistic_Object .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LinguisticDivisionType
:LinguisticDivisionType rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :DivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LinguisticToken
:LinguisticToken rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Token ,
  crm:E33_Linguistic_Object .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LiteraryCorpus
:LiteraryCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P46_is_composed_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :LiteraryTextResource
  ] ;
  rdfs:label "Literary Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LiteraryTextResource
:LiteraryTextResource rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :TextResource .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ManuallyAnnotatedCorpus
:ManuallyAnnotatedCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Manually Annotated Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MultimodalCorpus
:MultimodalCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Multimodal Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/NERTool
:NERTool rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Tool ;
  rdfs:label "Named Entity Recognition Tool"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/NewspaperCorpus
```

```
:NewspaperCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Newspaper Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/NormalizationTool
:NormalizationTool rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Tool ;
  rdfs:label "Normalization Tool"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/OCRDocument
:OCRDocument rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :TextRecognitionDocument .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/OralHistoryCorpus
:OralHistoryCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Oral History Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/POSTaggingTool
:POSTaggingTool rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Tool ;
  rdfs:label "Part-of-Speech Tagging and Lemmatization Tool"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Page
:Page rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P56_bears_feature ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :WrittenSpace
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ParallelCorpus
:ParallelCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Parallel Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ParliamentaryCorpus
:ParliamentaryCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Parliamentary Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PhysicalCodex
:PhysicalCodex rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :PhysicalManuscript ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P46_is_composed_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :PhysicalFolio
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PhysicalFolio
:PhysicalFolio rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :PhysicalTextBearingObject ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P56_bears_feature ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :PhysicalPageSide
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PhysicalManuscript
:PhysicalManuscript rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :PhysicalTextBearingObject .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PhysicalPageSide
:PhysicalPageSide rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Physical_Human-Made_Feature .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PhysicalTextBearingObject
:PhysicalTextBearingObject rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E22_Human-Made_Object .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Physical_Human-Made_Feature
:Physical_Human-Made_Feature rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E25_Human-Made_Feature .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Polygon
:Polygon rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ;
    rdfs:comment "A polygon defined by a series of points." ;
    rdfs:label "Polygon" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ReferenceCorpus
:ReferenceCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
    rdfs:label "Reference Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ScholarlyEdition
:ScholarlyEdition rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :TextResource ;
    rdfs:subClassOf ceo:ScholarlyEdition .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Segment
:Segment rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ,
        [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
          owl:onProperty crm:P128_carries ;
          owl:allValuesFrom :DocumentToken
        ] ,
        [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
          owl:onProperty crm:P56_bears_feature ;
          owl:allValuesFrom :Glyph
        ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/SegmentType
:SegmentType rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf crm:E55_Type .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/SentimentAnalysisTool
:SentimentAnalysisTool rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Tool ;
    rdfs:label "Sentiment Analysis Tool"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Shape
:Shape rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ;
    rdfs:comment "A shape associated with a text block, containing one or more polygons." ;
    rdfs:label "Shape" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/SignLanguageResources
:SignLanguageResources rdf:type owl:Class ;
    rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
    rdfs:label "Sign Language Resources"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/SpokenCorpus
```

```
:SpokenCorpus rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Corpus ;
  rdfs:label "Spoken Corpus"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextDivision
:TextDivision rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :Division ,
  :TextObject .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextDivisionType
:TextDivisionType rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :DivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextObject
:TextObject rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E73_Information_Object .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextPassage
:TextPassage rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :TextObject .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextRecognitionDocument
:TextRecognitionDocument rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :DocumentObject .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextRecognitionDocumentCollection
:TextRecognitionDocumentCollection rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :DocumentResource ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty crm:P46_is_composed_of ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :TextRecognitionDocument
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextResource
:TextResource rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE1_Dataset .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextToken
:TextToken rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :TextObject ,
  :Token .
:EditedTextToken rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :TextToken,
  ceo:EditedTextPassage .

:CriticalTextToken rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :TextToken,
  ceo:CriticalTextPassage .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Token
:Token rdf:type owl:Class ;
  rdfs:subClassOf :CharacterSequence ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty :has_token_part ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :Token
  ] ,
  [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
    owl:onProperty :has_token_type ;
    owl:allValuesFrom :TokenType
  ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TokenType
:TokenType rdf:type owl:Class ;
```

```

rdfs:subClassOf crm:E55_Type .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Tool
:Tool rdf:type owl:Class ;
      rdfs:subClassOf sshoc:SHE10_Tool ;
      rdfs:label "Tool"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Wordlist
:Wordlist rdf:type owl:Class ;
          rdfs:subClassOf :LexicalResource ;
          rdfs:label "Wordlist"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/WrittenSpace
:WrittenSpace rdf:type owl:Class ;
              rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ,
              [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
                owl:onProperty crm:P56_bears_feature ;
                owl:allValuesFrom :Zone
              ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/WrittenSpaceType
:WrittenSpaceType rdf:type owl:Class ;
                  rdfs:subClassOf crm:E55_Type .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Zone
:Zone rdf:type owl:Class ;
      rdfs:subClassOf :Digital_Human-Made_Feature ,
      [ rdf:type owl:Restriction ;
        owl:onProperty crm:P56_bears_feature ;
        owl:allValuesFrom :Line
      ] .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/ZoneType
:ZoneType rdf:type owl:Class ;
          rdfs:subClassOf crm:E55_Type .

### http://purl.org/critical-edition-ontology/CriticalEdition
#ceo:CriticalEdition rdf:type owl:Class .

### http://purl.org/critical-edition-ontology/ScholarlyEdition
#ceo:ScholarlyEdition rdf:type owl:Class .

### http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#wktLiteral
geo:wktLiteral rdf:type owl:Class .

### http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#List
rdf:List rdf:type owl:Class .

#####
# Individuals
#####

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/AncientGreek
:AncientGreek rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
               crm:E56_Language ;
               rdfs:label "Ancient Greek" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/CustomZone
:CustomZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              :ZoneType .

```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DamageZone
:DamageZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DefaultLine
:DefaultLine rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              :LineType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DigitizationArtefactZone
:DigitizationArtefactZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                            :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Div1
:Div1 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
        :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Div2
:Div2 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
        :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Div3
:Div3 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
        :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Div4
:Div4 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
        :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Div5
:Div5 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
        :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Div6
:Div6 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
        :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DropCapitalLine
:DropCapitalLine rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  :LineType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/DropCapitalZone
:DropCapitalZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/GraphicZone
:GraphicZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/HeadingLine
:HeadingLine rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              :LineType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/InterlinearLine
:InterlinearLine rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                 :LineType .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/IntertextualResearch
:IntertextualResearch rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                        crm:E55_Type ;
                        rdfs:label "intertextual research"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Latin
:Latin rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
        crm:E56_Language ;
        rdfs:label "Latin" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/LatinPoetry
:LatinPoetry rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              crm:E55_Type ;
              rdfs:label "Latin poetry"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MIUR
:MIUR rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
       :Legal_Body ;
       crm:P1_is_identified_by :PRIN_2005 ,
                               :PRIN_2007 ;
       rdfs:label "MIUR" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ
:MQDQ rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
       :LiteraryCorpus ;
       crm:P102_has_title :MQDQ_Title ;
       crm:P104_is_subject_to :MQDQ_License ;
       crm:P14_carried_out_by :MQDQ_Funding ;
       crm:P1_is_identified_by :MQDQ_Identifier ;
       crm:P2_has_type :IntertextualResearch ,
                      :LatinPoetry ,
                      :MetricalAnalysis ,
                      :WordRetrieval ;
       crm:P4_has_time-span :MQDQ_IssuedDate ;
       crm:P67_refers_to :MQDQ_ContactPerson ;
       crm:P72_has_language :AncientGreek ,
                            :Latin ;
       crm:P76_has_contact_point :MQDQ_AdvancedSearchLink ,
                                 :MQDQ_ProjectURL ;
       crm:P94i_was_created_by :MQDQ_Authors ,
                               :MQDQ_Publisher ;
       crm:P3_has_note :MQDQ_Description ;
       crm:P90_has_value :MQDQ_Size .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_AdvancedSearchLink
:MQDQ_AdvancedSearchLink rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                          :Contact_Point ;
                          rdfs:label "https://www.mqdq.it/public/ricerca/avanzata"^^xsd:anyURI .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_Authors
:MQDQ_Authors rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              crm:E39_Actor ;
              rdfs:label "AA. VV." .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_ContactPerson
:MQDQ_ContactPerson rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                    crm:E39_Actor ;
                    crm:P107_has_current_or_former_affiliation :CaFoscari_Venezia ;
                    crm:P131_is_identified_by :Paolo_Mastandrea .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_Description
:MQDQ_Description rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  crm:E33_Linguistic_Object ;
                  rdfs:label "Description of the Musisque Deoque (MQDQ) corpus."@en .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_Funding
:MQDQ_Funding rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
               crm:E11_Modification ;
               crm:P14_carried_out_by :MIUR .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_Identifier
:MQDQ_Identifier rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                 crm:E42_Identifier ;
                 rdfs:label "https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/OPEN-555"^^xsd:anyURI .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_IssuedDate
:MQDQ_IssuedDate rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  crm:E52_Time-Span ;
                  crm:P82a_begin_of_the_begin "2005-01-01"^^xsd:date .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_License
:MQDQ_License rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
               crm:E30_Right ;
               crm:P67_refers_to "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/"^^xsd:anyURI .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_ProjectURL
:MQDQ_ProjectURL rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  :Contact_Point ;
                  rdfs:label "http://www.mqdq.it"^^xsd:anyURI .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_Publisher
:MQDQ_Publisher rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                 crm:E39_Actor ;
                 rdfs:label "Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale 'A. Zampolli' - Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche (ILC-CNR)" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_Size
:MQDQ_Size rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
            crm:E54_Dimension ;
            crm:P90_has_value 2300000 ;
            crm:P91_has_unit "tokens" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MQDQ_Title
:MQDQ_Title rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
             crm:E35_Title ;
             rdfs:label "Musisque Deoque (MQDQ)"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MainZone
:MainZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
            :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MarginTextZone
:MarginTextZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MetricalAnalysis
:MetricalAnalysis rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                   crm:E55_Type ;
                   rdfs:label "metrical analysis"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/MusicZone
:MusicZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
            :ZoneType .
```

```
### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/NumberingZone
:NumberingZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PRIN_2005
:PRIN_2005 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
            crm:E42_Identifier ;
            rdfs:label "PRIN 2005" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PRIN_2007
:PRIN_2007 rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
            crm:E42_Identifier ;
            rdfs:label "PRIN 2007" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Paolo_Mastandrea
:Paolo_Mastandrea rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  crm:E21_Person ;
                  crm:P131_is_identified_by [ rdf:type :Actor_Appellation ;
                                             rdfs:label "Paolo Mastandrea"
                                           ] ;
                  crm:P76_has_contact_point "mast@unive.it" .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Paragraph
:Paragraph rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
               :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PoemLine
:PoemLine rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
            :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/PoemLineGroup
:PoemLineGroup rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                :TextDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/QuireMarksZone
:QuireMarksZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                 :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/RunningTitleZone
:RunningTitleZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
                  :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/SealZone
:SealZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
           :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/Sentence
:Sentence rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
           :LinguisticDivisionType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/SpaceSegment
:SpaceSegment rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
               :SegmentType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/StampZone
:StampZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
            :ZoneType .
```

```

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TableZone
:TableZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
           :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TextSegment
:TextSegment rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
           :SegmentType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/TitlePageZone
:TitlePageZone rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
           :ZoneType .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/WordRetrieval
:WordRetrieval rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              crm:E55_Type ;
              rdfs:label "word-retrieval"@en .

### http://cophilab.eu/ontologies/cophi/WrittenSpace
:WrittenSpace rdf:type owl:NamedIndividual ,
              :WrittenSpaceType .

#####
# Annotations
#####

geo:as_linestring rdfs:comment "Defines the baseline (=linestring) geometry in WKT format." ;
                 rdfs:label "as linestring" .

geo:as_polygon rdfs:comment "Defines the polygon geometry in WKT format." ;
               rdfs:label "as polygon" .

### Generated by the OWL API (version 4.5.25.2023-02-15T19:15:49Z) https://github.com/owlcs/owlapi

```